

SO-CHIC Cruise Report
December 2021/January 2022
S.A. AgulhasII

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Contents

1	Scientific Personnel	6
2	Cruise Track	6
3	Maud Rise Polynya: Southbound	11
4	Atmospheric Forcing	12
4.1	Radiation Sensors	12
5	CTD	
	Compiled by Nadine Steiger	12
5.1	CTD Operations	13
5.2	Initial data processing	18
5.3	Preliminary results of the CTD cross-sections	20
5.4	Conductivity sensor calibration	23
5.5	Temperature sensors	23
6	Salinometer	
	Compiled by Alexandra Azevedo and Bianca Soares	26
6.1	Sampling strategy	26
6.2	Salinity bottles	26
6.3	Sample analysis	26
6.4	Problems Encountered	27
6.5	Salinity conversion	27
7	Thermosalinograph	
	Compiled by Leon Jacobs	28
7.1	Underway sampling and TSG salinity calibration	28
8	XBT	
	Compiled by Leon Jacobs	31
9	Chlorophyll	
	Compiled by Hanna Rosenthal	32
9.1	Chlorophyll sampling, filtration and analysis	32
9.2	Stations	32
9.3	Chlorophyll calibration for CTD data	32
9.4	Chlorophyll calibration for Seaglider	34
9.5	Known Issues	34
10	Seawater carbonate chemistry (DIC, TA, pH and $p\text{CO}_2$)	
	Compiled by Siyabulela Hamnca	36
10.1	Dissolved Inorganic Carbon (DIC) and Titration Alkalinity (TA) Sampling	36
10.2	DIC and TA analysis	46
10.3	Continuous $p\text{CO}_2$ observations	46
10.4	Constraining the $p\text{CO}_2$ bias on SA Agulhas II	47
10.5	Marine pH measurements	47
10.6	References	47
11	Dissolved Oxygen (DO)	
	Compiled by Leon Jacobs	48
11.1	Future Recommendation	49
12	$\delta^{18}\text{O}$	
	Compiled by Nadine Steiger	49

13 Methane	
Compiled by Marcel du Plessis	50
14 Glider/Sailbuoy Operations	
Compiled by Marcel du Plessis	51
14.1 Seagliders	52
14.1.1 Deployment procedure	53
14.1.2 Typical timings for a deployment	53
14.1.3 Pre-deployment checks	54
14.1.4 Deployment of Seaglider SG640	54
14.1.5 Deployment of Seaglider SG675	54
14.2 Sailbuoy	55
14.2.1 Pre-deployment checks	56
14.2.2 Deployment	56
15 ASFAR (Autonomous System For Argo floats Release)	
Compiled by Sebastian Lavanchy	59
15.1 Preparation before deployment	59
15.2 Deployment	61
15.2.1 Notes	63
16 Carioca	
Compiled by Sebastian Lavanchy	64
16.1 Preparation before deployment	65
16.2 Deployment	66
17 Deep Arvor Floats	
Compiled by Sebastian Lavanchy	70
17.1 Preparation and deployment	70
18 Arvor Floats	
Compiled by Sebastian Lavanchy	73
18.1 Preparation and deployment	73
19 BioArgo	
Compiled by Sebastian Lavanchy	77
19.1 Preparation and deployment	77
20 UTempBuoy	
Compiled by Sebastian Lavanchy	79
20.1 Preparation and Deployment	80
21 PROPOL (Profiler for Polynya)	
Compiled by Sebastian Lavanchy	81
21.1 Preparation Before Deployment	83
21.2 Deployment	86
21.3 Triangulation	89
22 Upward Looking Sonar (ULS)	
Compiled by Sebastian Lavanchy	91
22.1 Preparation before deployment	92
22.2 Deployment	93
23 Air-Sea Interaction Profiler	
Compiled by Brian Ward and Anneke ten Doeschate	96

List of Figures

1	Complete cruise track of the SANAE61 voyage from Cape Town on December 3rd 2021 to Cape Town on January 29th 2022.	7
2	Conditions in which the S.A AgulhasII were stuck for almost 12 days. Upper: December 27th a few kilometres from Penguin Bukta. Lower: December 29th en route to Akta, breaking ice by rolling the ship.	10
3	Left: Sea ice forecast from the ECMWF on December 10th 2021 clearly indicating the presence of the MRP. Right: Location of the assets deployed within the MRP en route to Penguin Bukta.	11
4	Map of the locations of all CTD stations on top of the regional bathymetry (RTOPO-2, Schaffer et al. 2016). Color-coding of the stations corresponds to the different sections.	14
5	Section E: Temperature, Salinity, Oxygen and Fluorescence within the uppermost 1000m. Black lines mark isopycnals and diamonds show the station location and name.	20
6	Section W: Temperature, Salinity, Oxygen and Fluorescence within the uppermost 1000m. Black lines mark isopycnals and diamonds show the station location and name.	21
7	Section R: Temperature, Salinity, Oxygen and Fluorescence within the uppermost 1000m. Black lines mark isopycnals and diamonds show the station location and name.	21
8	Section N: Temperature, Salinity, Oxygen and Fluorescence within the uppermost 1000m. Black lines mark isopycnals and diamonds show the station location and name.	22
9	Comparison of the bottle salinity data from Sensor 1 with the sample salinity from the salinometer as a function of depth (a), as a histogram including all good data (b) and as a function of time (c). The flagged data (red in a and c) are data from stations 16, 18, and 19 and data above 100m.	24
10	Comparison of the bottle salinity data from Sensor 2 with the sample salinity from the salinometer as a function of depth (a), as a histogram including all good data (b) and as a function of time (c). The flagged data (red in a and c) are data from stations 16, 18, and 19 and data above 100m.	25
11	Surface temperature recorded with the TSG system (in color) on top of bathymetry contours.	29
12	Salinity and temperature (SBE45 in blue and SBE38 in black) during the time period of underway sampling. The salinity values from the underway samples analysed with the Portasal salinometer are marked with blue stars to compare with the salinity values from the TSG at the same time of the sampling (red stars).	30
13	Salinity measured with the TSG (averaged over 30s before and after the sampling) versus the salinity of the underway samples measured with the Portasal salinometer, together with the linear regression line and the corresponding values. Outliers on the 10th of January and after the 20th of January are removed.	30
14	Left: Location of south-bound XBT deployments. Right: Location of north-bound XBT deployments.	31
15	A) Filtration set up with sampling bottle (1), measuring cylinder (2), filtration flask (3), vials to put the filters in (4), pump (5). B) Analysis set up with Fluorometer (Turner Trilogy Benchtop Fluorometer) (6), Acteone bottle (7) and MilliQ bottle (8).	33
16	Comparison of chlorophyll measurements from CTD fluorescence sensor (WET Labs ECOAFL/FL) and samples. Note that the data displayed here has not been corrected for quenching.	34

17	Comparison of uncorrected fluorescence measured by the Seaglider and chlorophyll measured from samples taken for Niskin bottles on calibration cast.	35
18	Oxygen values from CTD (Y-axis) vs calculated winkler (X-axis), including linear regression.	48
19	Sealing of $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ sample bottle after the parafilm was used up.	49
20	SO-CHIC methane sampling map with RTopo-2.0 bedrock topography, with CTD methane sampling stations indicated by crosses.	50
21	Methane sampling meniscus type.	50
22	Deployment locations of the three autonomous robots during the SO-CHIC cruise represented by the red dots while background color shows the satellite derived chlorophyll-a concentration provided by Sentinel 3A, 3B and NOAA-20 VIIRS between 1-13 January 2022. The southern location represents the deployment of one Seaglider (SG640) and Sailbuoy (SB1812) while the northern dot a Seaglider (SG675). See Table 1 for their locations.	51
23	SG640 on the heli-deck undergoing testing on the SO-CHIC cruise.	52
24	Deployment of SG640 using the quick release off the aft crane.	53
25	Buoyancy position of SG640 in the water after 5 minutes.	54
26	Sailbuoy tied down on the heli-deck undergoing testing.	55
27	Deployment of the Sailbuoy on the aft crane using a quick release to the stern of the vehicle.	57
28	Sailbuoy sitting in the water and sailing away from the ship.	58
29	ASFAR before deployment.	60
30	Deep Arvor before and during deployment.	70
31	Arvor before and during deployment.	73
32	Bioargo before and during deployment.	77
33	The 3 types of UTempBuoys: 6 x iceBT60/40-17T3P (left); 6 x iceBTC2/40-11T0P (middle); 6 x iceBTC5/40-11T0P (right).	79
34	UTempBuoy deployments.	80
35	Schematic of PROPOL deployment strategy.	82
36	PROPOL triangulation pattern indicating the position of the mooring.	90
37	ULS deployment schematic.	91

List of Tables

1	Narrative of the different sections of the SANAE61 voyage on the S.A. AgulhasII. The SO-CHIC activities were embedded in this voyage.	9
2	Float deployments in Polynya.	11
3	CTD deployments in Polynya.	12
4	CTD station list with sampling overview and comments	15
4	Cont.	16
4	Cont.	17
5	List of stations where chlorophyll samples were taken.	32
6	SO-CHIC CTD sampling for DIC and TA.	45
7	SO-CHIC underway sampling for DIC and TA.	45
8	Platforms deployed during SO-CHIC cruise, including sensors, deployment date and location.	52
9	Deployment details of the ASFAR.	59
10	Deployment details of the Deep Arvor SN AD2700-18FR002.	71
11	Deployment details of the Deep Arvor SN AD2700-18FR003.	71
12	Deployment details of the Deep Arvor SN AD2700-18FR006.	72
13	Deployment details of the Deep Arvor SN AD2700-18FR019.	72
14	Deployment details of the Deep Arvor SN AI2600-21FR001.	74
15	Deployment details of the Deep Arvor SN AI2600-21FR002.	74
16	Deployment details of the Deep Arvor SN AI2600-21FR003.	75
17	Deployment details of the Deep Arvor SN AI2600-21FR004.	75
18	Deployment details of the Deep Arvor SN AI2600-21FR005.	76
19	Deployment details of the BioArgo SN lovbio097 OIN-15-S4-02.	78
20	Deployment details of the BioArgo SN lovbio096 OIN-15-S4-01.	78
21	Deployment details of the UtempBuoy for Site2 CTD Station 5 on the 08/01/2022.	81
22	Deployment details of the UtempBuoy for Site2 CTD Station 27 on the 11/01/2022.	81
23	PROPOL triangulation point 1 range and position.	89
24	PROPOL triangulation point 2 range and position.	89
25	PROPOL triangulation point 3 range and position.	90
26	Details of the ULS deployment.	93

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2 Cruise Track

The S.A. AgulhasII departed Capetown on December 3rd 2021 as part of the SANAE61 voyage to resupply the South African Antarctica Base (SANAE-IV), and to accommodate scientific activities, of which SO-CHIC was a component.

The complete cruise track of the voyage from December 3rd 2021 to January 29th 2022 is shown in Figure 1.

The SANAE61 voyage can be broken up into several sections, described in Table 1.

Figure 1: Complete cruise track of the SANAE61 voyage from Cape Town on December 3rd 2021 to Cape Town on January 29th 2022.

Start Date	End Date	Narrative
03-Dec-2021 17:00	13-Dec-2021 12:00 9.8d (9.8d)	Cape Town to Penguin Bukta: Southward voyage from Cape Town to Penguin Bukta. The voyage was smooth with calm weather conditions. The SO-CHIC activities during this section are described below.
13-Dec-2021 12:00	18-Dec-2021 19:30 5.3d (15.1d)	Offloading at Penguin: Commenced offloading of equipment bound for SANAE-IV. As there were no helicopters on the voyage, the maintenance personnel for SANAE-IV had to rely on the commercial company White Desert to transport them. However, weather conditions prevented any aircraft from flying at this time. Two of the CAT vehicles (25 tons) could not be offloaded at Penguin Bukta as the crane on the bow of the AgulhasII was unable to lift them over the ice shelf. Therefore it was decided that the ship should travel to Akta, where the ice shelf was much lower than at Penguin.
18-Dec-2021 19:30	30-Dec-2021 01:00 11.2d (26.3d)	Stuck in ice: Departed Penguin with the intention to move to Akta to offload the heavy vehicles. However, weather and ice conditions were such that the AgulhasII soon become stuck in ice and remained within sight of Penguin for over 11 days (Figure 2). During this period the Malik Arctica, who was resupplying the German base at Akta, was also stuck in ice. A combination of thick ice and strong southerly winds resulted in any lack of progress during this period.
30-Dec-2021 01:00	01-Jan-2022 03:00 2.1d (28.4d)	Departure for Akta: Although the distance from Penguin to Akta was only 111 NM, the journey required over 48 hours. This was due to the ice conditions en route.
01-Jan-2022 03:00	01-Jan-2022 10:30 0.3d (28.7d)	Offloading at Akta: At Akta, the heavy vehicles were offloaded and the remaining maintenance people departed for SANAE-IV via White Desert. The SO-CHIC science team, who had departed Cape Town with White Desert on the morning of New Year's Eve, arrived onboard.
01-Jan-2022 10:30	03-Jan-2022 11:00 2.0d (30.8d)	Return to Penguin: The return journey to Penguin took longer than usual, as several hours at Penguin were spent carving ice to prevent a build up as had happened previously.

03-Jan-2022 11:00	06-Jan-2022 19:30 3.4d (34.1d)	Offloading at Penguin: Fuel and equipment for SANAE-IV continued during this period. In addition, any remaining passengers were transported to SANAE-IV. Two of the SO-CHIC science team members also departed for Wolf Fang, where they would remain until a flight to Cape Town could be arranged.
06-Jan-2022 19:30	16-Jan-2022 00:30 9.2d (43.3d)	SO-CHIC dedicated cruise: This section is described in detail below.
16-Jan-2022 00:30	17-Jan-2022 08:00 1.3d (44.6d)	Return to Penguin: Steamed back to Penguin Bukta after the SO-CHIC activities at Maud Rise.
17-Jan-2022 08:00	19-Jan-2022 14:00 2.3d (46.9d)	Final operations for SANAE-IV: An additional fuel pump was conducted, and all equipment and people to return to Cape Town were received on board.
19-Jan-2022 14:00	23-Jan-2022 02:45 3.5d (50.4d)	Transit to SO-CHIC Site1: Left Penguin Bukta for the last time en route to the SO-CHIC Site1.
23-Jan-2022 02:45	23-Jan-2022 14:45 0.5d (50.9d)	SO-CHIC Site1 Activities: This section is described in detail below.
23-Jan-2022 14:45	29-Jan-2022 06:30 5.7d (56.6d)	Transit back to Cape Town

Table 1: Narrative of the different sections of the SANAE61 voyage on the S.A. AgulhasII. The SO-CHIC activities were embedded in this voyage.

Figure 2: Conditions in which the S.A AgulhasII were stuck for almost 12 days. Upper: December 27th a few kilometres from Penguin Bukta. Lower: December 29th en route to Akta, breaking ice by rolling the ship.

3 Maud Rise Polynya: Southbound

During the transit southward toward Antarctica, the Maud Rise Polynya (MRP) started to open, and by December 10th it was well established (Figure 3). In order to take advantage of this serendipity, we requested a small deviation of the S.A. AgulhasII to deploy assets, and conduct a single CTD cast. The details are provided in Tables 2 and 3.

Figure 3: Left: Sea ice forecast from the ECMWF on December 10th 2021 clearly indicating the presence of the MRP. Right: Location of the assets deployed within the MRP en route to Penguin Bukta.

Asset	Serial Number	Date	Time	Latitude	Longitude
Bio-Argo	P42308-19FR005	11-DEC-2021	15:01	64° 31.0' S (-64.517°)	1°30.0' E (1.50°)
Argo	AI2600-21FR105	11-DEC-2021	11:08	64° 0.052' S (-64.0009°)	1°29.14' E (1.4857°)
Argo	AI2600-21FR106	11-DEC-2021	11:08	64° 0.052' S (-64.0009°)	1°29.14' E (1.4857°)
Argo	AI2600-21FR107	11-DEC-2021	11:08	64° 0.052' S (-64.0009°)	1°29.14' E (1.4857°)
Argo	AI2600-21FR108	11-DEC-2021	11:08	64° 0.052' S (-64.0009°)	1°29.14' E (1.4857°)

Table 2: Float deployments in Polynya.

STN	Longitude	Latitude	Date	EA600 Depth (m)	CTD Depth (m)	Samples Taken	Comments
MRP	64° 31.800' S (-64.530)	1° 30.109' E (1.50182)	11-DEC-2021 15:12	3000	1000	S, DIC	Calibration CTD for the Bio-argo float

Table 3: CTD deployments in Polynya.

4 Atmospheric Forcing

There were two independent met stations on the AgulhasII: the Scientific Data System (SDS) and the South Africa Weather Service (SAWS) suite of sensors.

The list of met parameters from each station are listed below:

- SDS: relative humidity, barometric pressure, air temperature, wind speed, and wind direction. Data is provided every 1 minute.
- SAWS: air temperature, barometric pressure, dewpoint, relative humidity, wind direction, and wind speed. Data is provided every 5 minutes.

4.1 Radiation Sensors

Two longwave and two shortwave sensors were deployed on top of the crow's nest and were logged independently on a Campbell Scientific CR1000. Daily checks were made to ensure the clock did not drift significantly and to ensure integrity of the data logging.

5 CTD

Compiled by Nadine Steiger

In total, 67 CTD casts were conducted during the SO-CHIC cruise, with an extensive coverage over Maud Rise and 5 additional casts at 54° N (figure 4 and table 4).

Over Maud Rise, four high-resolution CTD sections were taken. Two sections (Section E and Section W) crossed the northern slope of Maud Rise at 3° 13' E to 3° 46' E and at about 2° 27' E, respectively. This had a latitudinal extent of 63° 30' S to 64° 32' S and 63° 18' S to 64° 30' S with a distance of about ~8.9 km distance between stations.

The sections crossed a front at around 64° 0' S (see Figure 4 and Table 4 for the station locations). The front was located based on the CTD data which then determined the deployment locations for the glider, Asfar, Uptemp Buoy, Arvor and the Sailbuoy.

As a result of completing sections E and W earlier than anticipated, another section (Section R) was added along the eastern ridge of Maud Rise at about 64° 40' S from the center of Maud Rise at 4° 44' E

eastward towards $7^{\circ} 34' E$. This transect was further extended westward from the center (Section Center-West) towards $0^{\circ} 06' E$. The section Center-West had a larger distance between stations (~ 17.6 km) and was continued until the time of return to Penguin Bukta.

Along Sections E, W and R, CTD casts were alternated between full depth and 1000 m depth. Water samples (DIC, S, $\delta^{18}O$, occasionally methane, Chlorophyll-A and DO; see Table 4 for information on the water samples) were taken at every deep station and at calibration stations. At Section Center-West, all CTD casts were full depth. Some stations had to be skipped due to icebergs or time constraint.

In addition to the CTD transects, CTD casts were carried out for sensor calibration at mooring/glider deployment locations between Penguin Bukta and Maud Rise, on top of Maud Rise and at the front on Section W.

At Site 1, 5 CTD stations were taken along the 0° -meridian leading towards the Glider-deployment station at $54^{\circ} 0' S$. These stations were only 750 m deep, and DIC and S were sampled at each station, with chlorophyll-A at the glider-deployment station for calibration. Time constraints allowed for every second planned station and prohibited a continuation of CTD stations northward of $54^{\circ} 0' S$.

The stations were labeled consecutively (stn***) and in agreement with the grid number of the ship (VOY-049-**) following the planned station numbers, thus there are gaps in the final station numbers where stations were skipped.

5.1 CTD Operations

The steel cable was used throughout the CTD operations and a rosette frame with 24 Niskin bottles and SBE 9plus CTD Unit and SBE 11plus V5.2 Deck Unit. Prior to the SO-CHIC part of the cruise, on the transit from Cape Town towards Penguin Bukta, the steel cable was checked and had to be shortened by about 10 m due to a bad kink, and the dead end and the underwater joint were consequently redone. There were additional minor kinks in the steel cable that were not cut off, but monitored by the crew throughout the CTD operations. There were no further issues with the steel cable.

A test CTD cast was taken on the southward transit to check the operation, instrumentation, and bottle firing. No further issues were encountered with the cable, rosette or electronics of the sensors. Once all SO-CHIC personnel were on board, another test CTD cast (stn 001) was carried out at the ice shelf at Penguin Bukta for familiarisation with the sampling process, the operation of the CTD, and to test the equipment again.

The winch and the CTD software were operated according to the ship protocols. Once on station, the CTD 2 deck unit was turned on and the Software Version Seasave V 7.22.5 was started. In communication with the SO-CHIC science team, the crew lowered the CTD to 10 m depth, where the pump turned on. After waiting for about 20s, the CTD was brought back up to the surface and lowered down again by the crew to 10 m depth.

The science team then took control of the CTD with a speed of 0.5 ms^{-1} towards the bottom of the thermocline and 1 ms^{-1} onward. For the deep stations, the CTD was stopped at 10 m above bottom. The altimeter sometimes only went on about 50 m above bottom and only showed stable values from about 40 m above bottom.

On the upcast of the deep CTD stations, typically 2 Niskin bottles were fired at 12 different depths to accelerate the sampling process and to have two bottles available in case of misfiring. The bottles

Figure 4: Map of the locations of all CTD stations on top of the regional bathymetry (RTOPO-2, Schaffer et al. 2016). Color-coding of the stations corresponds to the different sections.

	Station # (deployment)	Longitude	Latitude	NME UTC (Time @ stn)	Depth EA600 [m]	CTD depth [db]	Samples	Comments	
	1 Test	002 42.266 W	70 15.355 S	06-Jan-2022 16:41:05	314	250	DIC, O2, CH4, S, dO18, Chla	Test station	
	2 Deep A Arvor floats	000 28.813 E	68 00.007 S	07-Jan-2022 07:04:53	4533	4571	O2, S, dO18	Niskin 3: leaking bottle cap Seasave msg: FFF... Unsupported modem message: F9 FE FF from SBE carousel	
	3 Deep A Arvor Floats	000 02.974 E	67 29.988 S	07-Jan-2022 13:37:20	4622	4673	DIC, O2, CH4, S, dO18, Chla		
Section E	4 Propol	003 13.585 E	64 31.541 S	08-Jan-2022 09:24:24	2114	2095	DIC, O2, S, dO18, Chla	One of the red cups missing after cast -> forgotten to take off before? Data look okay	
	6 ULS, UptempA rvor, Bioargo	003 17.386 E	64 25.313 S	08-Jan-2022 22:20:48	2279	2260	DIC, S, dO18	Niskin 3 fired too quickly -> niskin 4 used instead (same depth)	
	7	003 19.818 E	64 20.764 S	09-Jan-2022 01:18:51	2429	1000	-		
	8	003 22.056 E	64 16.072 S	09-Jan-2022 03:06:04	2522	2507	DIC, O2, S, dO18	Niskin 11: CTD was moved up 1m just before firing bottle -> Niskin 12 used instead (same depth) CTD was not stopped at surface to fire bottles -> only 22 niskins fired in total	
	9	003 24.497 E	64 11.451 S	09-Jan-2022 06:03:53	2638	1002	-	Pump already turned on when CTD was still on deck	
	10	003 26.811 E	64 06.962 S	09-Jan-2022 07:41:19	2799	2796	DIC, O2, S, dO18	Seasave msg: FFF... Unsupported modem message from carousel Only 22 Niskins fired	
	11	003 29.478 E	64 02.306 S	09-Jan-2022 10:45:07	2997	1000	-		
	12	003 31.767 E	63 57.646 S	09-Jan-2022 12:28:02	3368	3377	DIC, O2, S, dO18		
	13	003 34.276 E	63 53.105 S	09-Jan-2022 15:55:35	3664	1001	-		
	14	Station was skipped due to iceberg							
	15	003 39.056 E	63 43.800 S	09-Jan-2022 17:55:11	4649	1000	-		
	16	003 41.556 E	63 39.284 S	09-Jan-2022 19:26:04	4708	4773	DIC, S, dO18		
	17	003 43.804 E	63 34.591 S	09-Jan-2022 23:49:46	4859	999	-		
	18	003 46.197 E	63 29.997 S	10-Jan-2022 01:28:33	4953	5011	DIC, S, dO18	Forgot to fire bottles at the bottom - > Niskin1 & 2 fired 23 mab	
Section W	19	002 26.892 E	63 17.938 S	10-Jan-2022 08:14:03	5204	5288	DIC, S, dO18	Niskin17: didn't fire -> sampled from Niskin 18 instead (same depth)	
	20	002 26.974 E	63 22.785 S	10-Jan-2022 12:43:27	4757	999	-		
	21	002 26.923 E	63 27.618 S	10-Jan-2022 15:50:40	4791	4862	DIC, O2, CH4, S, dO18, Chla	Niskin17: misfired	
	22	002 27.011 E	63 32.379 S	10-Jan-2022 20:08:45	4353	1000	-		
	23	002 26.864 E	63 37.165 S	10-Jan-2022 21:39:44	4217	4253	DIC, S, dO18	DIC sample 125 (Niskin 13) broke after sampling	

Table 4: CTD station list with sampling overview and comments

Section R	24	002 26.981 E	63 41.991 S	11-Jan-2022 01:23:48	3298	1000	-	Pump turned on before CTD went in the water
	25	002 26.965 E	63 46.774 S	11-Jan-2022 02:55:49	3169	3174	DIC, S, dO18	Niskin16 didn't close -> sampling S & dO18 from Niskin15
	26	002 27.104 E	63 51.621 S	11-Jan-2022 06:05:53	3052	1000	-	CTD stopped for about 3min on the upcast at wire out = 1050m (set for the downcast)
	27	002 26.601 E	63 39.455 S	11-Jan-2022 08:44:37	3786	3818	DIC, S, dO18	Asfar Station Originally planned as stn028, ship grid: VOY-049-27 -> ctd files are called 027
	28	002 26.916 E	63 56.392 S	11-Jan-2022 16:00:23	2719	2724	DIC, S, dO18	Originally planned as stn027, ship grid: VOY-049-28 -> ctd files are called 028
	29	002 26.956 E	64 01.171 S	11-Jan-2022 18:54:37	2596	2583	DIC, S, dO18	
	30	002 26.858 E	64 06.005 S	11-Jan-2022 21:42:28	2454	1002	-	
	31	002 26.908 E	64 10.711 S	11-Jan-2022 23:27:42	2358	2342	DIC, S, dO18	Seasave error msg: FFF Unsupported modem message: FF 06 35 from SBE carousel Niskin 3 & 5 did not show up as fired on Seasave, but they were actually closed.
	32	002 26.882 E	64 15.629 S	12-Jan-2022 02:14:21	2261	1000	-	
	33	002 26.959 E	64 20.373 S	12-Jan-2022 03:48:57	2188	2169	DIC, S, dO18	Temperatures on up vs downcast offset by ca. 0.1C between 500m and 120 m
	34	002 26.821 E	64 25.154 S	12-Jan-2022 06:17:21	2160	999	-	
	35	002 26.823 E	64 29.997 S	12-Jan-2022 07:56:14	2159	2141	DIC, S, dO18	
	36	004 44.764 E	64 45.551 S	12-Jan-2022 15:35:08	3013	3010	DIC, S, dO18	
	37	004 55.535 E	64 46.433 S	12-Jan-2022 18:40:54	3288	1000	-	
	38	005 06.259 E	64 47.374 S	12-Jan-2022 20:12:37	2349	2480	DIC, S, dO18	We stopped at 16 mab as the depth was already far below eco sounder depth
	39	005 17.001 E	64 48.292 S	12-Jan-2022 23:00:05	2028	1000	-	
	40	005 27.751 E	64 46.743 S	13-Jan-2022 00:31:32	1809	1801	S, dO18	CTD reached seafloor as change in altimeter stayed unnoticed. Everything looked fine after, we checked the sensor readings and the rosette, as well as the steel cable. Niskin 1 and 2 were fired at the bottom and might contain sediments.
	41	005 38.229 E	64 45.230 S	13-Jan-2022 03:03:48	1894	1000	-	
	42	005 48.782 E	64 43.724 S	13-Jan-2022 04:33:19	1948	1934	DIC, S	No dO18 bottles left for sampling
	43	005 59.583 E	64 42.198 S	13-Jan-2022 06:49:46	1718	999	-	
	44	006 10.140 E	64 40.672 S	13-Jan-2022 08:25:08	1508	1505	-	
	45	006 20.769 E	64 39.149 S	13-Jan-2022 10:20:05	1752	1001	DIC, S	

Table 4: Cont.

	46	006 31.154 E	64 37.732 S	13-Jan-2022 11:58:46	1855	1846	-		
	47	006 41.710 E	64 36.140 S	13-Jan-2022 14:01:00	2177	999	-		
	48	006 52.605 E	64 34.642 S	13-Jan-2022 15:36:17	2396	2501	DIC, S	CTD header file sounding = 4897 (given by bridge as EA600 showed 0).	
	49	007 02.605 E	64 33.111 S	13-Jan-2022 18:13:53	2297	999	-	Bottom depth in CTD header file is wrong (4600 m)	
	50	007 13.617 E	64 31.590 S	13-Jan-2022 19:41:19	4210	4260	DIC, S		
	51	007 23.959 E	64 30.097 S	13-Jan-2022 23:29:05	4915	999	-		
	52	007 34.676 E	64 28.579 S	14-Jan-2022 01:04:11	4922	4991	DIC, S		
Section Central -West	53	004 23.495 E	64 48.190 S	14-Jan-2022 11:32:19	2923	2927	Chl-a		
	54	004 02.161 E	64 50.912 S	14-Jan-2022 15:08:42	2657	2646		Power issue with hydraulic Aframe at surface. CTD was sent back to 10m. stopped data at 10m. CTD at surface for about 25 min	
	55	003 40.931 E	64 53.578 S	14-Jan-2022 18:47:58	2664	2654	DIC, S	Niskin 24 did not get fired -> Niskin 23 taken instead (same depth)	
	56	003 19.521 E	64 56.339 S	14-Jan-2022 22:10:33	2551	2537	-		
	57	Skipped due to ice berg							
	58	002 37.267 E	65 01.662 S	15-Jan-2022 02:13:19	1630	1628	DIC, S		
	59	002 29.920 E	65 00.003 S	15-Jan-2022 04:20:45	1305	1000	-		
	61	001 42.597 E	64 53.414 S	15-Jan-2022 08:25:04	2492	2578	-		
	62	001 24.269 E	64 50.820 S	15-Jan-2022 11:26:48	2579	2568	-		
	63	001 01.721 E	64 50.657 S	15-Jan-2022 14:21:14	2774	2767	DIC, S, Chl-a		
	64	Skipped due to time constraint							
	65	001 16.342 E	64 50.412 S	15-Jan-2022 18:26:58	3575	3559	3 surface bottles (Niskin 3,4,5) for underway DIC comparison	SDS CTD station labeled as station VOY-049-64, but called station 65 according to SO-CHIC plan. Bottom depth in CTD header is wrong (3382 m)	
	66	000 06.600 E	64 50.211 S	15-Jan-2022 21:36:49	3778	3796	DIC, S	SDS CTD station labeled as station VOY-049-65 Niskin 20 not fired -> water sample taken from 19 instead (same depth)	
		methane	002 43.042 E	77 14.349 S	17-Jan-2022 16:28:11	286	272	DIC, CH4, Chl-a	CTD station at Penguin bugta specifically for methane
Site 1	72	000 00.037 E	54 59.992 S	23-Jan-2022 02:54:18	1699	750	DIC, S		
	74	000 00.002 E	54 48.008 S	23-Jan-2022 05:16:03	1240	750	DIC, S	Winch stopped at 810m (wire out) on the way up for a few minutes	
	78	000 00.038 W	54 24.051 S	23-Jan-2022 08:19:16	2281	750	DIC, S		
	80	000 00.063 W	54 11.977 S	23-Jan-2022 11:00:06	2689	750	DIC, S		
	82 Glider & Carioca	000 00.070 E	54 00.005 S	23-Jan-2022 14:46:33	2458	750	DIC, S, Chl-a	Glider calibration cast	

Table 4: Cont.

were fired after about 30 min waiting time after stopping the CTD at the corresponding depth.

Once the CTD was on deck, the sensors were always covered with their cups and the O₂ sensor and pump was flushed with Milli-Q water. In case of longer breaks between the CTD stations, the CTD carousel was rinsed with fresh water.

Occasionally the CTD stopped on the upcast at the depth set for the downcast, causing a pause at that depth if not noticed immediately. The weather was generally good during CTD casts and there was no sea ice or temperatures too cold which caused any problems of freezing. Any issues that occurred during the CTD operations are listed in Table 4.

5.2 Initial data processing

All CTD data were processed on the CTD computer using the SBE Data processing software following the standard filters suggested for the SBE 9plus CTD unit. The processing procedure was following the standard procedure specific to the instruments used on the Agulhas II.

1. Convert data from hexadecimal binary (.hex/.dat) to converted data file (.cnv). The used configuration file was `9p-1284_Marion2021_new-altimeter.xmlcon`.
2. Wildedit
 - Standard deviations for pass one = 2
 - Standard deviations for pass two = 10
 - Scans per block = 100
 - Keep data within this distance of the mean = 0
 - Exclude scans marked bad = yes
 - Select Wildedit variables: Conductivity, Salinity, Oxygen, Turbidity
3. Cell Thermal Mass
 - Thermal anomaly amplitude [alpha] = 0.03
 - Thermal anomaly time constant [1/beta] = 7.0
4. Filter
 - Pressure = Low pass filter B, time constant [s] = 0.15
5. Loopedit
 - Minimum velocity type = Fixed minimum velocity
 - Minimum CTD velocity [ms^{-1}] = 0.25
 - Exclude scans marked bad = Yes
 - Remove surface soak = YES
6. Derive
 - Select derived variables: Salinity1 & 2, Sound velocity [Chen-Millero, ms^{-1}], Density [density, kg m^{-3}]
7. Binavg

- Bin type = Pressure
- Bin size = 1.0
- Exclude scans marked bad = Yes
- Scans to skip over = 0
- Cast to process = Upcast and Downcast

8. Bottle Summary

- Select Averaged variables: Select all sensor variables
- Select Derived variables: Select derived variables

9. Split

- Select input file
- Select Output files: Downcast, Upcast

10. ASCII Out

- Select input files: Whole cast, Downcast, Upcast

The processed CTD data for each station are saved in a file for the whole cast (`stn***.cnv`), the downcast only (`dstn***.cnv`), the upcast only (`ustn***.cnv`), and the bottle files (`stn***.bt1`) for the stations where samples were taken. The bottle files include all variables at the depth and the time at which the niskin bottles were fired.

5.3 Preliminary results of the CTD cross-sections

Figure 5 - Figure 7 show the temperature, salinity, oxygen and fluorescence at the uppermost 1000 m along the three transects over Maud Rise. Sections E and W (Figure 5 and Figure 6) reveal the location of the front at about $64^{\circ} 0' S$, which was used to determine the deployment location of the glider, Asfar, Uptemp Buoy, Arvor and the Sailbuoy for an intensive study. Figure 8 shows the CTD transect at the northern section.

Figure 5: Section E: Temperature, Salinity, Oxygen and Fluorescence within the uppermost 1000m. Black lines mark isopycnals and diamonds show the station location and name.

Figure 6: Section W: Temperature, Salinity, Oxygen and Fluorescence within the uppermost 1000m. Black lines mark isopycnals and diamonds show the station location and name.

Figure 7: Section R: Temperature, Salinity, Oxygen and Fluorescence within the uppermost 1000m. Black lines mark isopycnals and diamonds show the station location and name.

Figure 8: Section N: Temperature, Salinity, Oxygen and Fluorescence within the uppermost 1000m. Black lines mark isopycnals and diamonds show the station location and name.

5.4 Conductivity sensor calibration

The two conductivity sensors from the CTD were previously calibrated on 25/27 September 2019. To determine the drift and offset of the sensors during the cruise, the sensors were again calibrated after the cruise comparing the sensor conductivity values from the bottle data (.btl) with the salinity samples measured with the salinometer. During the cruise, no obvious issues with the conductivity sensors were noticed.

The two sensors show an average offset of 0.0032 psu and a relative drift of 8.1×10^{-5} psu/day. At the downcast of station 40, Sensor 4 has a sudden reduction in salinity by 0.1 psu within the depth range of 1682 db and 1772 db, but it returns to normal values again.

The salinity samples taken at stations 16, 18, and 19 differ by about 0.4 psu from the CTD sensor salinity, and those samples are consequently removed for the calibration. Only samples below 100 m are included in the calibration to consider more stable water masses and to exclude the depth-range with the largest difference between the two sensors and the water samples.

The difference between salinity values derived from the conductivity sensors and the sample salinity is shown in Figure 9 and Figure 10 for Sensor 1 and 2, respectively. Sensor 1 has a smaller mean offset (0.0029 psu) from the samples compared to Sensor 2 (0.0060 psu), and it has a smaller drift in time (4.2×10^{-5} psu/day compared to 11.4×10^{-5} psu/day for Sensor 2).

There is no apparent dependency on salinity with pressure for any of the sensors. We consequently suggest to use the measurements of Sensor 1. The use of Sensor 1 also eliminates the issue with Sensor 2 at station 40. The offset and the drift over the time period of measurements is smaller than the accuracy of the salinometer (0.003 psu) and the offset reduces to 0.0015 psu (Sensor 1) if only including the depths below 1000 m, where the water masses are more stable. Consequently, we decide to apply no further corrections to the salinity data.

5.5 Temperature sensors

The two temperature sensors from the CTD were sent calibrated on 25 September 2019. Comparing the measurements of the two sensors during the cruise shows an average offset of 3.72×10^{-5} °C and a relative drift of 3.36×10^{-6} °C. We conclude that the sensors do not need any correction and we suggest the use of temperature sensor 1.

Figure 9: Comparison of the bottle salinity data from Sensor 1 with the sample salinity from the salinometer as a function of depth (a), as a histogram including all good data (b) and as a function of time (c). The flagged data (red in a and c) are data from stations 16, 18, and 19 and data above 100m.

Figure 10: Comparison of the bottle salinity data from Sensor 2 with the sample salinity from the salinometer as a function of depth (a), as a histogram including all good data (b) and as a function of time (c). The flagged data (red in a and c) are data from stations 16, 18, and 19 and data above 100m.

6 Salinometer

Compiled by Alexandra Azevedo and Bianca Soares

6.1 Sampling strategy

Typically, 8 salinity samples were taken on the deep CTD casts for calibration of the CTD salinity sensor (see CTD section for details on the stations where water samples were taken). For the sampling, the salinity bottle and the plastic cup were rinsed three times with the Niskin water, then filled to the shoulder of the bottle to keep enough water for three readings on the salinometer, but at the same time to leave enough space to allow for gentle mixing before the analysis.

6.2 Salinity bottles

The salinity bottles presented for use, at the beginning of the voyage, all contained samples from a cruise completed in 2019. It was requested that these samples be analysed on board prior to using them. Majority of the bottles presented a high degree of crystallisation and as a result, required extensive cleaning after analysing.

The bottles were rinsed 3 times with Milli-Q water but still presented a salt film on the glass. They were then placed in the dishwasher to be cleaned and thereafter were rinsed 3 more times with Milli-Q water and allowed to dry fully before use. Only 45 salinity bottles were available, which prohibited the recommended waiting time of 24h before analysing the samples. Therefore, a water bath was prepared at room temperature, in which the samples were submerged for an hour. Thereafter, the samples were removed from the bath and allowed to equilibrate to room temperature for at least an hour. The sample temperatures were tested to ensure they had reached room temperature.

6.3 Sample analysis

The PORTASAL Model 8410A (accuracy of ± 0.003 psu) was used to obtain conductivity ratio values of the samples according to the procedure outlined below:

- Standardization
 - Performed every 24 hours, or if the bath temperature was changed.
 - The bath temperature was set to approximately 2°C above room temperature and adjusted in case if necessary. The room temperature was measured continuously and was about $19\pm 1^\circ\text{C}$. The standardization was started after the bath temperature stabilized.
 - Reference calibration was performed to obtain the – Reference, + Reference and Reference values, which would stabilize between 19750 and 19999.
 - Zero calibration performed to stabilize the conductivity ratio at 0.000 00.
 - Standard Sea Water (Batch P165) measurement was taken, using a sample of known conductivity ratio at 0.99986.
 - If the recorded conductivity ratio was not stable, the standardization process would be repeated.
- Sample Measurements
 - 8 samples were taken from various CTD casts and analysed with the salinometer.

- At the beginning of the analysis, each sample was gently rocked to ensure even mixing.
- The flow tube was cleaned, and the sample was installed, allowing it to fill the conductivity cell without the presence of air bubbles.
- The conductivity cell was filled and flushed 3 times and upon the fourth fill, the first conductivity ratio was taken.
- Three conductivity ratios were taken, in order to obtain an average. Any remarks regarding the sample, bottle or caps were written down in the log sheets.
- For comparison of the salinity calculation, one salinity reading per sample was noted down.
- This process was carried out across all 8 samples.
- Upon completion of the samples, the salinometer was flushed 3 times with Milli-Q water to ensure no crystallisation formed on the conductivity cell electrodes.

6.4 Problems Encountered

The stations on the 8th of January 2022 were only analysed on the 9th of January due to the conductivity ratio being unstable. The filter light had turned on and after reading the manual and attempts to solve the problem, the issue still persisted. The salinometer was turned off and standardization was redone but accurate conductivity ratios could still not be recorded. The morning of the 9th of January 2021, the filter button labelled ‘FLT’ was pressed and re-standardization was done. This seemed to resolve the issue and analysing of samples was resumed.

6.5 Salinity conversion

The three conductivity ratios (R_t) from the salinometer for each sample were averaged and converted into salinity using the MATLAB function `sw_sals.m` that follows the calculation 6.6.3.3 of the Guideline for Model 8410A Portasal (including the conversion of the bath temperature T from ITS-90 to IPTS-68).

7 Thermosalinograph

Compiled by Leon Jacobs

Surface temperature and salinity data were collected for the duration of the voyage using a SeaBird (SBE45) Thermosalinograph (TSG). Surface seawater is supplied to the instrument via the onboard seawater supply manifold, with surface water being pumped by centrifugal pumps from the sea-chest, located in the engine room. An additional SBE38 temperature sensor (serial no. 0705) is located at the sea-chest intake and this data is simultaneously relayed to the TSG deck unit and recorded with the TSG data. The TSG was setup to record data every six seconds. Data is logged using the Seabird SeaSave (version: 7.26.7.107) software, and is simultaneously relayed to the Scientific Data System (SDS).

The underway system was started using pump 1 on December 3rd 2021, after leaving the port of Cape Town. The underway system was left to run at least an hour prior to the TSG system being switched on, and data logging commenced at 20:26 (GMT). A complete record of the TSG is shown in Figure 11.

During the voyage excessive salinity spikes in the data were observed. The TSG system was flushed with a 1% tritonX solution on two occasions (05/12/2021 and 05/01/2022), to mitigate the situation.

An average of 2.98°C was observed between the SBE45 (TSG) and SBE38 (hull inlet) temperature sensors. The offset is most likely caused vessel heating and length of plumbing in between the two sensors. At certain points in time the difference between the two sensors was as great as 20.13°C (Figure 12). This difference was as a result of the valve to the TSG being closed off, and represents the difference between the hull inlet temperature and the air temperature at the SBE45 as there was no water flow.

During the south bound leg of the voyage, no TSG data was collected from 60° S towards the ice shelf (70° S) and the subsequent data was saved into a different directory. After ending the data acquisition, the data logging might have failed to started immediately. The data logging was restarted again on January 5th.

7.1 Underway sampling and TSG salinity calibration

Underway water samples for calibration of the TSG salinity measurements and for $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ analysis were collected from the underway system every 6 hours from January 7th until January 12th for $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ (when all sampling bottles were used) and until January 23rd for salinity (with a reduced temporal resolution of every 12 hours from 16 of January). In addition, the flow rate was measured during every sampling to monitor a consistent water flow.

The salinity samples analysed on January 10th (66,73,78,83) have an offset of > 0.4 psu compared to the TSG data (Figure 13). Issues with the salinometer or the standardization (see description of salinometer) are ignored. There is also a larger offset of > 0.15 psu from January 20th onward, which could also arise from issues with the analysis of the salinity samples, as the water samples after that date were all analysed together.

Figure 11: Surface temperature recorded with the TSG system (in color) on top of bathymetry contours.

Figure 12: Salinity and temperature (SBE45 in blue and SBE38 in black) during the time period of underway sampling. The salinity values from the underway samples analysed with the Portasal salinometer are marked with blue stars to compare with the salinity values from the TSG at the same time of the sampling (red stars).

Figure 13: Salinity measured with the TSG (averaged over 30s before and after the sampling) versus the salinity of the underway samples measured with the Portasal salinometer, together with the linear regression line and the corresponding values. Outliers on the 10th of January and after the 20th of January are removed.

8 XBT

Compiled by Leon Jacobs

A total 326 XBTs were successfully deployed throughout the duration of the voyage. 163 XBTs were deployed on the southern bound leg and 163 XBTs were deployed on the northern bound leg. XBT deployments were occasionally canceled due to unfavourable weather conditions, which resulted in the XBT copper wire snapping prematurely.

On the Southern bound leg (see figure 14), XBT deployments started on the 04/12/2021 and proceeded until the 13/12/2021. XBTs were deployed every 90min, between Cape Town and 50°S, at which point the resolution was increased to every 60min, depending on the vessel speed. On the southern bound leg the vessel passed through the MRP (64° S-66° S) at which point the XBT deployment rate was increased to every 30mins, to study this feature in greater depth.

On the Northern bound leg (see figure 14) XBT deployments started on the 19/01/2022 and proceeded until the 28/01/2022. XBTs were deployed every 60min, between the Antarctic Shelf and 50° S, at which point the resolution was decreased to every 90min, depending on the vessel speed. All XBT data recorded while at sea, will be submitted to the NOAA database.

Figure 14: Left: Location of south-bound XBT deployments. Right: Location of north-bound XBT deployments.

9 Chlorophyll

Compiled by Hanna Rosenthal

During the SO-CHIC cruise, Team Polar Gliders from Gothenburg University (Marcel du Plessis, Theo Spira, and Hanna Rosenthal) were responsible for chlorophyll sampling and analysis. Chlorophyll analysis was performed for two reasons: firstly to calibrate the fluorescence sensor on the on board CTD and secondly to calibrate the fluorescence sensor on the two Seagliders deployed during this voyage. As such we chose seven station to sample chlorophyll, two of which were taken within an hour of the Seaglider deployments.

9.1 Chlorophyll sampling, filtration and analysis

From CTD Niskin bottles 750-1000 ml Seawater samples were collected in 1L plastic sampling bottles(Fig 1A, 1). Immediately after collection 250ml of the water samples were filtered after through 25mm Whatman Glasfiber Filters. After filtering, each filter was placed in glass vials (Fig. 1A, 4) containing 8ml of 90% acetone and stored in a -20°C freezer for ~12-24 h. Samples were allowed to acclimate to room temperature for 30min in a closed drawer before the raw Chl-a fluorescence was measured using a Turner Trilogy Benchtop Fluorometer (Fig. 1B, 6Model: # 7200-0000, Serial # 720001027, non acidification module).

9.2 Stations

During the cruise 75 chlorophyll samples were taken at seven different station (Table 5). They were filtered right away. Two CTD casts and chlorophyll samples were taken within one hour of the Seglider deployment to use as calibration for the gliders sensors.

Station	Date [DD.MM.YY] Time [GMT]	Latitude	Longitude	Section	#samples
1 (Test)	6.01.22 16:44	70° 15.355 S	02° 42.260 E	test	6
3	7.01.22 13:51	67° 29.988 S	00° 02.974 E	deepA	12
4	8.01.22 11:38	64° 31.541 S	03° 13.584 E	PROPO L	12
21(Glider depl.)	10.01.22 15:55	63° 27.618 S	02° 26.923 E	W	11
63	15.01.22 14:26	64° 50.657 S	01° 01.721 E	R	13
Methane	17.01.22 16:58	70° 14.350 S	02° 43.043 E	Shelf	10
82 (Glider depl.)	23.01.22 14:52	54° 00.005 S	00° 00.070 E	Site 1	11

Table 5: List of stations where chlorophyll samples were taken.

9.3 Chlorophyll calibration for CTD data

Initial comparison between bottle samples and CTD florescence sensor (WET Labs ECO-AFL/FL) were made and indicate that the CTD sensor works well and has an offset of $f(x) = 0.123x + 0.0763$ (Figure 16).

- 1** Sample bottle
- 2** Measuring cylinder
- 3** Filtration flask
- 4** Vial
- 5** Pump
- 6** Fluorometer
- 7** Acetone bottle
- 8** MilliQ bottle

Figure 15: A) Filtration set up with sampling bottle (1), measuring cylinder (2) , filtration flask (3), vials to put the filters in (4), pump (5). B) Analysis set up with Fluorometer (Turner Trilogy Benchtop Fluorometer) (6), Acetone bottle (7) and MilliQ bottle (8).

Figure 16: Comparison of chlorophyll measurements from CTD fluorescence sensor (WET Labs ECOAFL/FL) and samples. Note that the data displayed here has not been corrected for quenching.

9.4 Chlorophyll calibration for Seaglider

Calibration cast was taken within an hour of both glider deployments. As an example the comparison with chlorophyll measured in water samples taken from the calibration cast and a linear fit of Seaglider 640 is shown in Figure 17.

9.5 Known Issues

- The CTD chlorophyll data is not quenching corrected
- Inverting the sampling bottle before filtering is recommended to ensure that the chlorophyll is equally distributed before filtering.
- Power plug for fluorometer stopped working. We used a alternative power supply to power the fluorometer during this cruise.

Figure 17: Comparison of uncorrected fluorescence measured by the Seaglider and chlorophyll measured from samples taken for Niskin bottles on calibration cast.

10 Seawater carbonate chemistry (DIC, TA, pH and $p\text{CO}_2$)

Complied by Siyabulela Hamnca

10.1 Dissolved Inorganic Carbon (DIC) and Titration Alkalinity (TA) Sampling

From 28 CTD stations, 398 DIC and TA samples ((348 samples at site 2 and 50 samples at site 1) were collected from every second CTD cast from 12 depths (10 at site 1) with increased resolution in shallower depths (Table 6).

A clear silicone rubber was connected to the niskin bottle outlet from the sea water manifold. The 500 mL borosilicate sample bottle was rinsed 3 times with a small amount of sea water, then filled and allowed overflow for the same amount of time it took to fill. The silicone rubber was then swiftly drawn out with water so the level drops to 1mm below the stopper. The samples were poisoned with 50% Mercuric chloride in the fume cupboard. The samples were stored in the sample bottle in the crate with the rubber over the stopper to stop it coming loose.

Additionally, 21 underway samples were also collected and the same sampling procolot using the underway seawater supply was followed. Underway DIC and TA samples were also collected along the Good Hope line (southward and northward leg) (Table 7).

Bottle	Station	Cast	Niskin	Depth	Temp	Salinity	Lat	Lon
SOC070122001	3	1	2	4673	-0.28	34.65	67.75	0.27
SOC070122002	3	1	4	3499	-0.21	34.65	67.75	0.27
SOC070122003	3	1	6	2000	0.06	34.67	67.75	0.27
SOC070122004	3	1	8	499	0.76	34.69	67.75	0.27
SOC070122005	3	1	10	324	0.96	34.7	67.75	0.27
SOC070122006	3	1	12	175	0.91	34.67	67.75	0.27
SOC070122007	3	1	14	123	0.33	34.6	67.75	0.27
SOC070122008	3	1	16	89	-1.03	34.44	67.75	0.27
SOC070122009	3	1	18	60	-1.68	34.3	67.75	0.27
SOC070122010	3	1	20	34	-1.4	34.2	67.75	0.27
SOC070122011	3	1	22	21	-0.89	34.02	67.75	0.27
SOC070122012	3	1	24	11	-0.82	34.02	67.75	0.27
SOC080122013	4	1	1	2095	-0.147	34.65	64.67	3.38
SOC080122014	4	1	3	1320	0.103	34.67	64.67	3.38
SOC080122015	4	1	5	660	0.382	34.68	64.67	3.38
SOC080122016	4	1	7	249	0.277	34.66	64.67	3.38
SOC080122017	4	1	9	140	-0.02	34.63	64.67	3.38
SOC080122018	4	1	11	100	-1.17	34.54	64.67	3.38
SOC080122019	4	1	13	69	-1.53	34.47	64.67	3.38
SOC080122020	4	1	15	49	-1.3	34.29	64.67	3.38
SOC080122021	4	1	17	30	-0.69	34.21	64.67	3.38
SOC080122022	4	1	19	15	-0.61	34.21	64.67	3.38
SOC080122023	4	1	21	10	-0.64	34.21	64.67	3.38
SOC080122024	4	1	23	5	-0.02	34.16	64.67	3.38
SOC080122025	6	1	1	2260	-0.14	34.66	64.5	3.39
SOC080122026	6	1	4	1502	0.099	34.67	64.5	3.39
SOC080122027	6	1	5	900	0.318	34.68	64.5	3.39
SOC080122028	6	1	7	460	0.419	34.68	64.5	3.39

SOC080122029	6	1	9	151	0.313	34.66	64.5	3.39
SOC080122030	6	1	11	109	-0.191	34.61	64.5	3.39
SOC080122031	6	1	13	80	-1.07	34.54	64.5	3.39
SOC080122032	6	1	15	50	-1.51	34.46	64.5	3.39
SOC080122033	6	1	17	40	-1.4	34.3	64.5	3.39
SOC080122034	6	1	19	25	-0.3	34.14	64.5	3.39
SOC080122035	6	1	21	20	-0.29	34.11	64.5	3.39
SOC080122036	6	1	23	10	-0.11	34.06	64.5	3.39
SOC080122037	8	1	1	2507	-0.12	34.66	64.29	3.38
SOC080122038	8	1	3	1599	0.066	34.67	64.29	3.38
SOC080122039	8	1	5	900	0.327	34.68	64.29	3.38
SOC080122040	8	1	7	400	0.31	34.67	64.29	3.38
SOC080122041	8	1	9	270	0.44	34.67	64.29	3.38
SOC080122042	8	1	12	150	0.28	34.65	64.29	3.38
SOC080122043	8	1	13	99	-0.77	34.57	64.29	3.38
SOC080122044	8	1	15	60	-1.5	34.44	64.29	3.38
SOC080122045	8	1	17	46	-0.81	34.15	64.29	3.38
SOC080122046	8	1	19	30	-0.65	34.12	64.29	3.38
SOC080122047	8	1	21	15	-0.16	34.09	64.29	3.38
SOC090122048	10	1	1	2791	-0.16	34.66	64.37	3.66
SOC090122049	10	1	3	2100	-0.05	34.67	64.37	3.66
SOC090122050	10	1	5	1200	0.25	34.67	64.37	3.66
SOC090122051	10	1	7	900	0.37	34.68	64.37	3.66
SOC090122052	10	1	9	413	0.58	34.69	64.37	3.66
SOC090122053	10	1	11	150	0.37	34.69	64.37	3.66
SOC090122054	10	1	13	89	-0.83	34.53	64.37	3.66
SOC090122055	10	1	15	49	-1.34	34.38	64.37	3.66
SOC090122056	10	1	17	37	-1.42	34.12	64.37	3.66
SOC090122057	10	1	19	28	-0.7	33.75	64.37	3.66
SOC090122058	10	1	21	4	-0.2	33.69	64.37	3.66
SOC090122059	12	1	1	3377	-0.21	34.65	64.13	3.73
SOC090122060	12	1	3	2800	-0.12	34.66	64.13	3.73
SOC090122061	12	1	5	1749	0.14	34.67	64.13	3.73
SOC090122062	12	1	7	1050	0.44	34.68	64.13	3.73
SOC090122063	12	1	9	475	0.6	34.68	64.13	3.73
SOC090122064	12	1	11	154	1.26	34.69	64.13	3.73
SOC090122065	12	1	13	60	0.36	34.56	64.13	3.73
SOC090122066	12	1	15	50	-0.29	34.45	64.13	3.73
SOC090122067	12	1	17	32	-0.63	34	64.13	3.73
SOC090122068	12	1	19	20	-0.04	33.91	64.13	3.73
SOC090122069	12	1	21	9	0.03	33.88	64.13	3.73
SOC090122070	12	1	23	5	0.08	33.88	64.13	3.73
SOC090122071	16	1	1	4773	-0.24	34.65	63.73	3.76
SOC090122072	16	1	3	2500	-0.03	34.67	63.73	3.76
SOC090122073	16	1	5	1501	0.33	34.68	63.73	3.76
SOC090122074	16	1	7	799	0.71	34.69	63.73	3.76
SOC090122075	16	1	9	250	1.27	34.69	63.73	3.76
SOC090122076	16	1	11	108	0.8	34.58	63.73	3.76
SOC090122077	16	1	13	80	-0.15	34.48	63.73	3.76
SOC090122078	16	1	15	61	-1.3	34.32	63.73	3.76

SOC090122079	16	1	17	45	-0.88	34.19	63.73	3.76
SOC090122080	16	1	19	30	0.1	34.07	63.73	3.76
SOC090122081	16	1	21	21	0.21	34.05	63.73	3.76
SOC090122082	16	1	23	10	0.28	34.04	63.73	3.76
SOC100122083	18	1	1	5011	-0.24	34.65	63.75	3.82
SOC100122084	18	1	3	3000	-0.13	34.66	63.75	3.82
SOC100122085	18	1	5	1500	0.32	34.68	63.75	3.82
SOC100122086	18	1	7	599	0.92	34.71	63.75	3.82
SOC100122087	18	1	9	250	1.26	34.7	63.75	3.82
SOC100122088	18	1	11	120	1.04	34.63	63.75	3.82
SOC100122089	18	1	13	80	-0.22	34.48	63.75	3.82
SOC100122090	18	1	15	60	-0.77	34.35	63.75	3.82
SOC100122091	18	1	17	45	-1.02	34.25	63.75	3.82
SOC100122092	18	1	19	26	-0.57	34.17	63.75	3.82
SOC100122093	18	1	21	16	-0.29	34.13	63.75	3.82
SOC100122094	18	1	23	7	0.35	34.05	63.75	3.82
SOC100122095	19	1	1	5288	-0.36	34.64	63.54	2.68
SOC100122096	19	1	3	4399	-0.36	34.65	63.54	2.68
SOC100122097	19	1	5	2750	-0.2	34.66	63.54	2.68
SOC100122098	19	1	7	1099	0.26	34.68	63.54	2.68
SOC100122099	19	1	9	220	0.76	34.67	63.54	2.68
SOC100122100	19	1	11	143	0.31	34.58	63.54	2.68
SOC100122101	19	1	13	100	-1.55	34.3	63.54	2.68
SOC100122102	19	1	15	63	-1.68	34.21	63.54	2.68
SOC100122103	19	1	17	39	-0.48	34.18	63.54	2.68
SOC100122104	19	1	19	30	-0.15	34.17	63.54	2.68
SOC100122105	19	1	21	14.8	0.16	34.04	63.54	2.68
SOC100122106	19	1	23	4	0.4	34.03	63.54	2.68
SOC100122107	21	1	1	4862	-0.39	34.64	63.62	2.69
SOC100122108	21	1	3	4001	-0.27	34.66	63.62	2.69
SOC100122109	21	1	5	2499	-0.12	34.66	63.62	2.69
SOC100122110	21	1	7	499	0.69	34.69	63.62	2.69
SOC100122111	21	1	9	160	0.94	34.65	63.62	2.69
SOC100122112	21	1	12	121	-0.58	34.59	63.62	2.69
SOC100122113	21	1	13	100	-0.28	34.48	63.62	2.69
SOC100122114	21	1	14	90	-0.77	34.42	63.62	2.69
SOC100122115	21	1	15	70	-1.4	34.27	63.62	2.69
SOC100122116	21	1	19	40	-0.48	34.16	63.62	2.69
SOC100122117	21	1	21	10	0.18	34.15	63.62	2.69
SOC100122118	21	1	23	5	0.4	34.17	63.62	2.69
SOC100122119	23	1	1	4253	-0.29	34.66	63.67	2.53
SOC100122120	23	1	3	3000	-0.19	34.66	63.67	2.53
SOC100122121	23	1	5	1500	0.25	34.68	63.67	2.53
SOC100122122	23	1	7	450	1.01	34.708	63.67	2.53
SOC100122123	23	1	9	230	1.28	34.7	63.67	2.53
SOC100122124	23	1	11	90	0.88	34.61	63.67	2.53
SOC100122125	23	1	13	71	0.26	34.53	63.67	2.53
SOC100122126	23	1	15	56	-0.79	34.42	63.67	2.53
SOC100122127	23	1	17	40	-0.84	34.24	63.67	2.53
SOC100122128	23	1	19	26	-0.43	34.13	63.67	2.53

SOC100122129	23	1	21	10	0.12	34.1	63.67	2.53
SOC100122130	23	1	23	6	0.42	34.11	63.67	2.53
SOC110122131	25	1	1	3174	-0.22	34.66	63.99	2.7
SOC110122132	25	1	3	2101	0.03	34.66	63.99	2.7
SOC110122133	25	1	5	1300	0.34	34.68	63.99	2.7
SOC110122134	25	1	7	600	0.77	34.7	63.99	2.7
SOC110122135	25	1	9	200	1.22	34.7	63.99	2.7
SOC110122136	25	1	11	100	0.98	34.64	63.99	2.7
SOC110122137	25	1	13	70	0.54	34.37	63.99	2.7
SOC110122138	25	1	15	45	-1.085	34.35	63.99	2.7
SOC110122139	25	1	17	35	-1.098	34.33	63.99	2.7
SOC110122140	25	1	19	25	-0.32	34.15	63.99	2.7
SOC110122141	25	1	21	20	0.011	34.13	63.99	2.7
SOC110122142	25	1	23	10	0.102	34.02	63.99	2.7
SOC110122143	28	1	1	3818	-0.23	34.65	63.78	2.6
SOC110122144	28	1	3	2799	-0.14	34.66	63.78	2.6
SOC110122145	28	1	5	1600	0.23	34.67	63.78	2.6
SOC110122146	28	1	7	800	0.63	34.69	63.78	2.6
SOC110122147	28	1	9	189	1.21	34.68	63.78	2.6
SOC110122148	28	1	11	90	0.58	34.6	63.78	2.6
SOC110122149	28	1	13	59	-0.5	34.47	63.78	2.6
SOC110122150	28	1	15	47	-0.89	34.38	63.78	2.6
SOC110122151	28	1	17	40	-0.96	34.36	63.78	2.6
SOC110122152	28	1	19	29	-0.91	34.23	63.78	2.6
SOC110122153	28	1	21	14	0.11	34.1	63.78	2.6
SOC110122154	28	1	23	3	0.34	34.66	63.78	2.6
SOC110122155	27	1	1	2724	-0.18	34.66	64.03	2.68
SOC110122156	27	1	3	2400	-0.1	34.66	64.03	2.68
SOC110122157	27	1	5	1499	0.13	34.67	64.03	2.68
SOC110122158	27	1	7	599	0.44	34.68	64.03	2.68
SOC110122159	27	1	9	299	0.39	34.67	64.03	2.68
SOC110122160	27	1	11	149	0.19	34.64	64.03	2.68
SOC110122161	27	1	13	89	-1.08	34.52	64.03	2.68
SOC110122162	27	1	15	50	-1.56	34.28	64.03	2.68
SOC110122163	27	1	17	29	-0.96	34.9	64.03	2.68
SOC110122164	27	1	19	19	-0.25	33.81	64.03	2.68
SOC110122165	27	1	21	9	0.16	33.75	64.03	2.68
SOC110122166	27	1	23	3	0.25	33.75	64.03	2.68
SOC110122167	29	1	1	2583	-0.13	34.66	64.07	2.7
SOC110122168	29	1	3	2100	-0.07	34.66	64.07	2.7
SOC110122169	29	1	5	1500	0.11	34.67	64.07	2.7
SOC110122170	29	1	7	900	0.36	34.68	64.07	2.7
SOC110122171	29	1	9	180	0.45	34.67	64.07	2.7
SOC110122172	29	1	11	125	0.03	34.64	64.07	2.7
SOC110122173	29	1	13	101	-1.11	34.52	64.07	2.7
SOC110122174	29	1	15	80	-1.49	34.5	64.07	2.7
SOC110122175	29	1	17	45	-1.6	34.37	64.07	2.7
SOC110122176	29	1	19	30	-1.22	34.1	64.07	2.7
SOC110122177	29	1	21	20	-0.4	33.82	64.07	2.7
SOC110122178	29	1	23	10	-0.17	33.8	64.07	2.7

SOC120122179	31	1	1	2342	-0.122	34.66	64.37	2.69
SOC120122180	31	1	4	1500	0.08	34.67	64.37	2.69
SOC120122181	31	1	5	1000	0.28	34.68	64.37	2.69
SOC120122182	31	1	7	500	0.35	34.67	64.37	2.69
SOC120122183	31	1	9	160	0.28	34.66	64.37	2.69
SOC120122184	31	1	11	119	-0.3	34.6	64.37	2.69
SOC120122185	31	1	13	90	-1	34.54	64.37	2.69
SOC120122186	31	1	15	45	-1.64	34.36	64.37	2.69
SOC120122187	31	1	17	35	-1.42	34.17	64.37	2.69
SOC120122188	31	1	19	25	-0.73	33.95	64.37	2.69
SOC120122189	31	1	21	15	0.1	33.89	64.37	2.69
SOC120122190	31	1	23	10	0.11	33.89	64.37	2.69
SOC120122191	33	1	1	2169	-0.19	34.65	64.43	2.7
SOC120122192	33	1	3	1500	-0.04	34.67	64.43	2.7
SOC120122193	33	1	5	1000	0.23	34.67	64.43	2.7
SOC120122194	33	1	7	550	0.4	34.68	64.43	2.7
SOC120122195	33	1	9	180	0.37	34.67	64.43	2.7
SOC120122196	33	1	11	140	0.28	34.65	64.43	2.7
SOC120122197	33	1	13	100	-1.05	34.55	64.43	2.7
SOC120122198	33	1	15	60	-1.56	34.44	64.43	2.7
SOC120122199	33	1	17	40	-1.06	34.14	64.43	2.7
SOC120122200	33	1	19	20	-0.24	33.95	64.43	2.7
SOC120122201	33	1	21	15	0.24	33.9	64.43	2.7
SOC120122202	33	1	23	10	0.26	33.9	64.43	2.7
SOC120122203	35	1	1	2141	-0.18	34.65	64.76	2.66
SOC120122204	35	1	3	1750	0	34.66	64.76	2.66
SOC120122205	35	1	5	1250	0.14	34.67	64.76	2.66
SOC120122206	35	1	7	999	0.25	34.67	64.76	2.66
SOC120122207	35	1	9	619	0.38	34.68	64.76	2.66
SOC120122208	35	1	11	249	0.32	34.66	64.76	2.66
SOC120122209	35	1	13	125	-0.4	34.5	64.76	2.66
SOC120122210	35	1	15	58	-1.56	34.45	64.76	2.66
SOC120122211	35	1	17	31	-0.7	34.07	64.76	2.66
SOC120122212	35	1	19	14	0.06	33.95	64.76	2.66
SOC120122213	35	1	21	10	0.17	33.96	64.76	2.66
SOC120122214	35	1	23	5	0.19	33.96	64.76	2.66
SOC120122215	36	1	1	310	-0.18	34.66	64.9	4.95
SOC120122216	36	1	3	2400	-0.09	34.66	64.9	4.95
SOC120122217	36	1	5	1198	0.29	34.68	64.9	4.95
SOC120122218	36	1	7	400	0.69	34.69	64.9	4.95
SOC120122219	36	1	9	119	1.02	34.69	64.9	4.95
SOC120122220	36	1	11	76	0.8	34.65	64.9	4.95
SOC120122221	36	1	13	65	0.55	34.6	64.9	4.95
SOC120122222	36	1	15	50	-0.26	34.44	64.9	4.95
SOC120122223	36	1	17	40	-0.39	34.25	64.9	4.95
SOC120122224	36	1	19	30	0.12	34.16	64.9	4.95
SOC120122225	36	1	21	15	0.35	34.15	64.9	4.95
SOC120122226	36	1	23	2	0.47	34.13	64.9	4.95
SOC120122227	38	1	1	2480	-0.04	34.66	64.88	5.17
SOC120122228	38	1	3	1500	0.23	34.68	64.88	5.17

SOC120122229	38	1	5	850	0.45	34.68	64.88	5.17
SOC120122230	38	1	7	301	1	34.7	64.88	5.17
SOC120122231	38	1	9	150	1.19	34.7	64.88	5.17
SOC120122232	38	1	11	60	1.14	34.66	64.88	5.17
SOC120122233	38	1	13	56	0.78	34.6	64.88	5.17
SOC120122234	38	1	15	40	-0.38	34.4	64.88	5.17
SOC120122235	38	1	17	30	-0.42	34.19	64.88	5.17
SOC120122236	38	1	19	19	0.48	34.08	64.88	5.17
SOC120122237	38	1	21	15	0.48	34.08	64.88	5.17
SOC120122238	38	1	23	10	0.49	34.08	64.88	5.17
SOC130122239	42	1	1	1934	0.08	34.67	64.92	6.02
SOC130122239	42	1	3	1501	0.22	34.68	64.92	6.02
SOC130122241	42	1	5	1000	0.44	34.69	64.92	6.02
SOC130122242	42	1	7	400	0.79	34.69	64.92	6.02
SOC130122243	42	1	9	130	0.93	34.67	64.92	6.02
SOC130122244	42	1	11	90	0.65	34.62	64.92	6.02
SOC130122245	42	1	13	70	0.25	34.57	64.92	6.02
SOC130122246	42	1	15	56	-0.25	34.44	64.92	6.02
SOC130122247	42	1	17	46	-0.56	34.34	64.92	6.02
SOC130122248	42	1	19	36	-0.29	34.16	64.92	6.02
SOC130122249	42	1	21	20	-0.29	34.09	64.92	6.02
SOC130122250	42	1	23	10	-0.29	34.09	64.92	6.02
SOC130122251	45	1	1	1001	0.5	34.68	64.69	6.55
SOC130122252	45	1	3	750	0.58	34.68	64.69	6.55
SOC130122253	45	1	5	374	0.96	34.7	64.69	6.55
SOC130122254	45	1	7	143	1.2	34.68	64.69	6.55
SOC130122255	45	1	9	43	-0.29	34.29	64.69	6.55
SOC130122256	45	1	11	30	0.42	34.11	64.69	6.55
SOC130122257	45	1	13	14	0.55	34.11	64.69	6.55
SOC130122258	45	1	15	4	0.58	34.11	64.69	6.55
SOC130122259	48	1	1	2501	-0.003	34.66	64.75	7.04
SOC130122260	48	1	3	2100	0.03	34.66	64.75	7.04
SOC130122261	48	1	5	1500	0.27	34.68	64.75	7.04
SOC130122262	48	1	7	899	0.57	34.69	64.75	7.04
SOC130122263	48	1	9	600	0.8	34.7	64.75	7.04
SOC130122264	48	1	11	180	1.19	34.69	64.75	7.04
SOC130122265	48	1	13	80	0.93	34.63	64.75	7.04
SOC130122266	48	1	15	60	0.31	34.56	64.75	7.04
SOC130122267	48	1	17	48	0	34.4	64.75	7.04
SOC130122268	48	1	19	29	0.29	34.13	64.75	7.04
SOC130122269	48	1	21	15	0.58	34.11	64.75	7.04
SOC130122270	48	1	23	3	0.66	34.12	64.75	7.04
SOC130122271	50	1	1	4260	-0.23	34.65	64.68	7.39
SOC130122272	50	1	3	2300	0.01	34.67	64.68	7.39
SOC130122273	50	1	5	1200	0.45	34.68	64.68	7.39
SOC130122274	50	1	7	450	1.04	34.71	64.68	7.39
SOC130122275	50	1	9	211	1.27	34.69	64.68	7.39
SOC130122276	50	1	11	120	1.04	34.64	64.68	7.39
SOC130122277	50	1	13	69	-1	34.41	64.68	7.39
SOC130122278	50	1	15	55	-1.1	34.3	64.68	7.39

SOC130122279	50	1	17	45	-0.91	34.26	64.68	7.39
SOC130122280	50	1	19	35	-0.49	34.19	64.68	7.39
SOC130122281	50	1	21	20	0.31	34.12	64.68	7.39
SOC130122282	50	1	23	10	0.39	34.12	64.68	7.39
SOC140122283	52	1	1	4991	-0.24	34.65	64.63	7.68
SOC140122284	52	1	3	3000	-0.14	34.66	64.63	7.68
SOC140122285	52	1	5	1500	0.33	34.68	64.63	7.68
SOC140122286	52	1	7	699	0.81	34.7	64.63	7.68
SOC140122287	52	1	9	260	1.25	34.69	64.63	7.68
SOC140122288	52	1	11	149	1.02	34.65	64.63	7.68
SOC140122289	52	1	13	90	0.45	34.55	64.63	7.68
SOC140122290	52	1	15	60	-1.39	34.37	64.63	7.68
SOC140122291	52	1	17	45	-1.43	34.29	64.63	7.68
SOC140122292	52	1	19	30	-0.4	34.11	64.63	7.68
SOC140122293	52	1	21	20	-0.06	34.05	64.63	7.68
SOC140122294	52	1	23	10	-0.01	34.04	64.63	7.68
SOC140122295	55	1	1	2654	-0.14	34.66	64.9	3.68
SOC140122296	55	1	3	2200	-0.07	34.66	64.9	3.68
SOC140122297	55	1	5	1374	0.19	34.67	64.9	3.68
SOC140122298	55	1	7	550	0.49	34.69	64.9	3.68
SOC140122299	55	1	9	210	0.52	34.67	64.9	3.68
SOC140122300	55	1	11	150	0.11	34.63	64.9	3.68
SOC140122301	55	1	13	88	-1.16	34.51	64.9	3.68
SOC140122302	55	1	15	61	-1.46	34.43	64.9	3.68
SOC140122303	55	1	17	51	-1.12	34.3	64.9	3.68
SOC140122304	55	1	19	31	0.14	34.19	64.9	3.68
SOC140122305	55	1	21	19	0.18	34.16	64.9	3.68
SOC140122306	55	1	23	10	0.19	34.16	64.9	3.68
SOC150122307	58	1	1	1628	0.04	34.67	65.2	2.7
SOC150122308	58	1	3	1000	0.19	34.68	65.2	2.7
SOC150122309	58	1	7	490	0.39	34.68	65.2	2.7
SOC150122310	58	1	9	180	-0.22	34.62	65.2	2.7
SOC150122311	58	1	11	70	-0.47	34.45	65.2	2.7
SOC150122312	58	1	13	55	-1.3	34.34	65.2	2.7
SOC150122313	58	1	15	40	-0.98	34.29	65.2	2.7
SOC150122314	58	1	17	15	-0.01	34.18	65.2	2.7
SOC150122315	63	1	1	2767	-0.2	34.65	64.02	1.22
SOC150122316	63	1	3	2100	-0.02	34.66	64.02	1.22
SOC150122317	63	1	5	1498	0.18	34.67	64.02	1.22
SOC150122318	63	1	7	900	0.43	34.68	64.02	1.22
SOC150122319	63	1	9	167	0.72	34.68	64.02	1.22
SOC150122320	63	1	11	80	0.25	34.58	64.02	1.22
SOC150122321	63	1	13	60	-0.62	34.47	64.02	1.22
SOC150122322	63	1	15	43	-1.18	34.3	64.02	1.22
SOC150122323	63	1	17	34	-0.94	34.03	64.02	1.22
SOC150122324	63	1	19	25	-0.09	34.88	64.02	1.22
SOC150122325	63	1	21	15	0.28	34.77	64.02	1.22
SOC150122326	63	1	23	4	0.26	34.77	64.02	1.22
SOC150122327	66	1	1	3796	-0.22	34.65	64.89	0.27
SOC150122328	66	1	3	2500	-0.04	34.66	64.89	0.27

SOC150122329	66	1	5	1501	0.28	34.68	64.89	0.27
SOC150122330	66	1	7	821	0.44	34.67	64.89	0.27
SOC150122331	66	1	9	310	0.71	34.67	64.89	0.27
SOC150122332	66	1	11	118	0.35	34.6	64.89	0.27
SOC150122333	66	1	13	79	-0.41	34.5	64.89	0.27
SOC150122334	66	1	15	62	-0.63	34.42	64.89	0.27
SOC150122335	66	1	17	45	-1.39	34.32	64.89	0.27
SOC150122336	66	1	19	30	-1.01	33.7	64.89	0.27
SOC150122337	66	1	21	20	-0.13	33.6	64.89	0.27
SOC150122338	66	1	23	11	-1.12	33.61	64.89	0.27
SOC170122339	67	1	1	272	-1.93	34.24	70.33	2.73
SOC170122340	67	1	3	240	-1.96	34.23	70.33	2.73
SOC170122341	67	1	5	200	-1.96	34.21	70.33	2.73
SOC170122342	67	1	7	150	-1.93	34.17	70.33	2.73
SOC170122343	67	1	9	120	-1.79	34.08	70.33	2.73
SOC170122344	67	1	11	90	-1.65	33.97	70.33	2.73
SOC170122345	67	1	13	60	-1.64	33.9	70.33	2.73
SOC170122346	67	1	15	40	-1.66	33.87	70.33	2.73
SOC170122347	67	1	17	20	-1.45	33.76	70.33	2.73
SOC170122348	67	1	19	10	-1.44	33.75	70.33	2.73
SOC230122349	72	1	1	750	1.63	34.72	55.26	0
SOC230122350	72	1	3	399	1.86	34.63	55.26	0
SOC230122351	72	1	5	301	1.8	34.57	55.26	0
SOC230122352	72	1	7	230	1.42	34.47	55.26	0
SOC230122353	72	1	9	181	0.63	34.3	55.26	0
SOC230122354	72	1	11	139	-1.06	34	55.26	0
SOC230122355	72	1	13	101	-1.03	33.88	55.26	0
SOC230122356	72	1	15	70	0.35	33.72	55.26	0
SOC230122357	72	1	17	40	1.22	33.62	55.26	0
SOC230122358	72	1	19	10	1.34	33.67	55.26	0
SOC230122359	74	1	1	751	1.54	34.71	54.8	0
SOC230122360	74	1	3	379	1.84	34.64	54.8	0
SOC230122361	74	1	5	301	1.63	34.57	54.8	0
SOC230122362	74	1	7	225	1.11	34.45	54.8	0
SOC230122363	74	1	9	185	-0.28	34.16	54.8	0
SOC230122364	74	1	11	150	-0.9	33.96	54.8	0
SOC230122365	74	1	13	102	-0.62	33.83	54.8	0
SOC230122366	74	1	15	80	0.4	33.73	54.8	0
SOC230122367	74	1	17	40	1.38	33.67	54.8	0
SOC230122368	74	1	19	10	1.54	33.67	54.8	0
SOC230122369	78	1	1	751	1.5	34.7	54.41	0.01
SOC230122370	78	1	5	401	1.75	34.64	54.41	0.01
SOC230122371	78	1	7	299	1.62	34.56	54.41	0.01
SOC230122372	78	1	9	202	0.3	34.27	54.41	0.01
SOC230122373	78	1	11	162	-0.5	34.05	54.41	0.01
SOC230122374	78	1	12	100	0.64	33.91	54.41	0.01
SOC230122375	78	1	13	80	0.38	33.85	54.41	0.01
SOC230122376	78	1	14	60	1.67	33.81	54.41	0.01
SOC230122377	78	1	18	20	1.7	33.81	54.41	0.01
SOC230122378	78	1	19	4	1.86	33.81	54.41	0.01

SOC230122379	80	1	1	753	1.5	34.7	54.45	0.02
SOC230122380	80	1	3	400	1.75	34.64	54.45	0.02
SOC230122381	80	1	5	270	1.6	34.54	54.45	0.02
SOC230122382	80	1	7	200	0.6	34.32	54.45	0.02
SOC230122383	80	1	9	141	-0.64	34.04	54.45	0.02
SOC230122384	80	1	11	98	-0.09	33.89	54.45	0.02
SOC230122385	80	1	13	74	1.3	33.82	54.45	0.02
SOC230122386	80	1	15	60	1.7	33.8	54.45	0.02
SOC230122387	80	1	17	41	1.8	33.79	54.45	0.02
SOC230122388	80	1	19	10	2	33.76	54.45	0.02
SOC230122389	82	1	1	1000	1.19	34.71	54	0.02
SOC230122390	82	1	3	450	1.7	34.65	54	0.02
SOC230122391	82	1	5	201	0.7	34.34	54	0.02
SOC230122392	82	1	7	151	0.13	34.16	54	0.02
SOC230122393	82	1	9	86	0.02	33.89	54	0.02
SOC230122394	82	1	11	76	0.39	33.86	54	0.02
SOC230122395	82	1	13	59	1.22	33.79	54	0.02
SOC230122396	82	1	15	35	1.7	33.17	54	0.02
SOC230122397	82	1	17	24	1.8	33.76	54	0.02
SOC230122398	82	1	19	10	1.8	33.76	54	0.02
SOC230122367	74	1	17	40	1.38	33.67	54.8	0
SOC230122368	74	1	19	10	1.54	33.67	54.8	0
SOC230122369	78	1	1	751	1.5	34.7	54.41	0.01
SOC230122370	78	1	5	401	1.75	34.64	54.41	0.01
SOC230122371	78	1	7	299	1.62	34.56	54.41	0.01
SOC230122372	78	1	9	202	0.3	34.27	54.41	0.01
SOC230122373	78	1	11	162	-0.5	34.05	54.41	0.01
SOC230122374	78	1	12	100	0.64	33.91	54.41	0.01
SOC230122375	78	1	13	80	0.38	33.85	54.41	0.01
SOC230122376	78	1	14	60	1.67	33.81	54.41	0.01
SOC230122377	78	1	18	20	1.7	33.81	54.41	0.01
SOC230122378	78	1	19	4	1.86	33.81	54.41	0.01
SOC230122379	80	1	1	753	1.5	34.7	54.45	0.02
SOC230122380	80	1	3	400	1.75	34.64	54.45	0.02
SOC230122381	80	1	5	270	1.6	34.54	54.45	0.02
SOC230122382	80	1	7	200	0.6	34.32	54.45	0.02
SOC230122383	80	1	9	141	-0.64	34.04	54.45	0.02
SOC230122384	80	1	11	98	-0.09	33.89	54.45	0.02
SOC230122385	80	1	13	74	1.3	33.82	54.45	0.02
SOC230122386	80	1	15	60	1.7	33.8	54.45	0.02
SOC230122387	80	1	17	41	1.8	33.79	54.45	0.02
SOC230122388	80	1	19	10	2	33.76	54.45	0.02
SOC230122389	82	1	1	1000	1.19	34.71	54	0.02
SOC230122390	82	1	3	450	1.7	34.65	54	0.02
SOC230122391	82	1	5	201	0.7	34.34	54	0.02
SOC230122392	82	1	7	151	0.13	34.16	54	0.02
SOC230122393	82	1	9	86	0.02	33.89	54	0.02
SOC230122394	82	1	11	76	0.39	33.86	54	0.02
SOC230122395	82	1	13	59	1.22	33.79	54	0.02
SOC230122396	82	1	15	35	1.7	33.17	54	0.02

SOC230122397	82	1	17	24	1.8	33.76	54	0.02
SOC230122398	82	1	19	10	1.8	33.76	54	0.02

Table 6: SO-CHIC CTD sampling for DIC and TA.

Bottle	Station	Cast	Niskin	Depth	Temp	Salinity	Lat	Lon
SAN051221001	0	0	0	0	25	35	38.38	11.54
SAN051221002	0	0	0	0	25	35	38.97	11.25
SAN051221003	0	0	0	0	25	35	39.59	10.73
SAN051221004	0	0	0	0	25	35	40.32	10.1
SAN061221005	0	0	0	0	25	35	40.92	9.52
SAN061221006	0	0	0	0	25	35	41.66	9.07
SAN061221007	0	0	0	0	25	35	42.36	8.49
SAN061221008	0	0	0	0	25	35	43.11	7.96
SAN061221009	0	0	0	0	25	35	43.53	7.44
SAN061221010	0	0	0	0	25	35	44.31	6.93
SAN071221011	0	0	0	0	25	35	44.93	6.09
SAN071221012	0	0	0	0	25	35	45.54	5.54
SAN071221013	0	0	0	0	25	35	46.08	5.22
SAN071221014	0	0	0	0	25	35	46.97	4.58
SAN071221015	0	0	0	0	25	35	47.34	4.06
SAN071221016	0	0	0	0	25	35	48.05	3.36
SAN081221017	0	0	0	0	25	35	48.84	2.68
SAN081221018	0	0	0	0	25	35	49.45	2.06
SAN081221019	0	0	0	0	25	35	50.08	1.5
SAN081221020	0	0	0	0	25	35	50.87	0.82
SAN081221021	0	0	0	0	25	35	51.47	0.36
SAN081221022	0	0	0	0	25	35	52.19	0.01
SAN091221023	0	0	0	0	25	35	53.22	0.01
SAN091221024	0	0	0	0	25	35	54.22	0
SAN091221025	0	0	0	0	25	35	55.14	0
SAN091221026	0	0	0	0	25	35	55.84	0.05
SAN091221027	0	0	0	0	25	35	56.85	0.28
SAN091221028	0	0	0	0	25	35	57.69	0.01
SAN101221029	0	0	0	0	25	35	58.58	0
SAN101221030	0	0	0	0	25	35	59.56	0.16
SAN101221031	0	0	0	0	25	35	60.12	0.16
SAN101221032	0	0	0	0	25	35	60.7	0.22
SAN101221033	0	0	0	0	25	35	61.32	0.29
SAN101221034	0	0	0	0	25	35	61.99	0
SAN111221035	0	0	0	0	25	35	62.46	0.84
SAN210122036	0	0	0	0	25	35	64.59	0.24
SAN210122037	0	0	0	0	25	35	63.7	0.01
SAN210122038	0	0	0	0	25	35	62.49	0.22
SAN210122039	0	0	0	0	25	35	61.52	0.24

Table 7: SO-CHIC underway sampling for DIC and TA.

10.2 DIC and TA analysis

The CTD 398 samples in the borosilicate 500 mL were analysed on board using Mirianda's VINDTA 3C (Versatile Instrument for the Determination of Titration Alkalinity). Both DIC and TA are measured in parallel with a VINDTA 3C instrument (MARIANDA, Kiel). The accuracy was set by internationally recognized and widely used certified reference material (CRM), batch 185, obtained from Prof. A. Dickson at Scripps Institute of Oceanography (USA). DIC is the sum of all dissolved inorganic carbon species and is determined by a precise coulometric method [Dickson et al, 2007]. Two CRMs were measured in duplicate at the beginning and the end of the analyses. The differences in the measurements of CRMs deduces the precision of the instrument. The TA measurements were made by potentiometric titration with a strong acid (HCl) as a titrant. The acid consumption up to the second endpoint is equivalent to the titration/total alkalinity. The system uses a highly precise Metrohm Titrino for adding acid, a pH electrode and a reference electrode. The measurement temperature for both DIC and TA was 25°C.

10.3 Continuous $p\text{CO}_2$ observations

Before the southward leg from Cape Town a few minor problems were experienced. The equilibrator (EQU) gas flow pump was not working properly therefore the instrument was shut down. On the 1st of December in of the SOCHIC cruise, the equilibrator pump was serviced. The instrument responded positively however there was emergency shutdown of the instrument caused by leakage in the EQU H_2O sensor the causing the peristaltic pumps to change the level in the equilibrator and thus $p\text{CO}_2$ measurements. The EQU H_2O sensor was also serviced by blowing drying it. The licor gas flow sensor also stopped working and the flow was measured manually for the remainder of the cruise using a measuring cylinder to estimate flow from the equilibrator. To ensure the quality of the output data, instrument was flushed several times with zero and span standards on the licor test panel.

Partial pressure of carbon dioxide ($p\text{CO}_2$) in the ocean and atmosphere was measured for all but southward leg of SANAE 61 and the first 2 days of the SOCHIC cruise. The difference in $p\text{CO}_2$ represents the thermodynamic driving potential for CO_2 gas transfer across the sea surface.

The underway(UW) automated flowing $p\text{CO}_2$ measuring System from General Oceanics $p\text{CO}_2$ with a Licor-LI7000 Infra-red gas detector was used for the continuous $p\text{CO}_2$ observations starting from the 09/01/22. This UW- $p\text{CO}_2$ system is designed to operate continuously fully automatically. The seawater enters the system at a rate of 3-3.5 Litres min^{-1} via a three-way valve, which can act as an emergency shut-off valve, and then passes through a 200 mm filter before entering the Equilibrator through a spiral nozzle. The nozzle creates a spray of water that maximizes the rate of CO_2 equilibration process between the seawater and the headspace gas contained in the equilibrator.

The seawater exits the equilibrator over a stand pipe covered by an "inverted cup", which effectively isolates the headspace gas from the ambient air. The top of the standpipe is vented to the outside so that pressure or suction in the drain line will not affect the equilibrator. The headspace inside the equilibrator is maintained at ambient pressure by a vent. The dry gas is then sent to the Infrared LICOR analyser (the LICOR) where its CO_2 and H_2O mole fractions ($x\text{CO}_2$ and $x\text{H}_2\text{O}$) are measured. Atmospheric air is also being measured alternatively by the system. A dedicated pump (ATM pump) constantly draws outside air, a portion of which is dried in a second channel of the condenser and flushes the content of a small reservoir (the ballast), a short length of PVC pipe which is open to the ambient air. The dry ballast atmospheric air is circulated through the LICOR for analysis. Four reference gases were used: 0.00, 284.22, 399.19 and 410.03 ppm, provided and cross-calibrated to international standards by the GAW station at Cape Point. The instrument cycle included returning to these gases followed by atmospheric measurements once every six hours.

10.4 Constraining the $p\text{CO}_2$ bias on SA Agulhas II

The $p\text{CO}_2$ bias of a ship is the difference between the $p\text{CO}_2$ observed by the instrument on the ship and the water at the intake. This arises from the bacterial growth in the pipes of the Scientific Water Supply and it is highly temperature sensitive. It needs to be carried out spanning a range of temperatures that are representative of the cruise track. The essence of the protocol is that water samples are collected with near surface ($\pm 5\text{-}7\text{m}$), representative of the depth of the intake. This protocol was conducted by triggering three separate Niskin bottles from the same depth but 5 seconds apart. Simultaneously with triggering the Niskin bottles, 3 replicates from the water supply in the underway lab were collected. From each Niskin bottle This protocol was repeated 3 times during the cruise in warm (38°S), cool (48°S), and cold (64°S) waters to obtain a good confidence in the temperature dependence of the bias correction. This was done to provide a useful mean to overcome the uncertainty that comes from the ship roll.

10.5 Marine pH measurements

SeaFET from Sea-Bird Electronics was used for the continuous pH measurements. The primary sensor element of the SeaFET is the ISFET, a solid-state sensor that senses pH in marine environments. The ISFET has two reference electrodes: an internal reference and an external reference, that give separate reference potentials to the ISFET and show separate pH values (pH Internal and pH External). After the corrections for temperature and salinity are applied, the values from the internal and external are similar, and let the user verify the validity of the sensor's measurements.

10.6 References

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11 Dissolved Oxygen (DO)

Compiled by Leon Jacobs

DO samples were collected from selected CTD stations. DO samples were analyzed using the 848 titrino plus on onboard the vessel, for the purpose of calibrating the CTD, wave profiler and glider.

Unfortunately the analysis of DO samples had to be cancelled, due to inconsistent measurements during the standardization of the instrument. Over a period of three days stretching from the 05/01/2022 to 07/01/2022, the instrument reached end point standardization volumes ranging from 2.5637 mL to 5.9475 mL, using the same method and chemical reagents. Three different scientists attempted the standardization process to eliminated human error, to no avail.

On the 08/01/2022 standardization were reattempted, and 27 standards were analysed, with only the measurements of the last 6 standards not exceeding a difference of 0.05 ml/L. Usually 3 consecutive readings within 0.05ml/L would be sufficient but due to the observed inconsistencies, 6 consecutive samples were used instead. All DO samples collected until this point needed to be disposed of as they exceeded the 12 hour period for analysing the sample.

On the 09/01/2022, three standards were analysed measuring 5.0171, 5.0197 and 5.0252. Using the average (5.020667) of the above mentioned standards, the first set of 10 DO samples were analysed, and compared to CTD values, see relationship in Figure 18. On the 10/01/2022, three consistent standards could not be obtained, due to air bubbles in the tubing. The titro was dosed to eliminate the bubbles. Unfortunately the bubbles were due to the Thiosulphate reagent running low, and all further DO analysis had to be cut short.

Since only 10 DO samples were analysed, it could unfortunately not be used for the calibration of the CTD, wave profiler and glider as originally intended.

Figure 18: Oxygen values from CTD (Y-axis) vs calculated winkler (X-axis), including linear regression.

11.1 Future Recommendation

It is recommended that for future cruises that a spare Titro set is packed along with spare chemical reactant and reagents, in order to have sufficient reactants/reagents.

12 $\delta^{18}\text{O}$

Compiled by Nadine Steiger

At every deep station, 8 $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ samples were taken at the same depths as salinity. Further $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ samples were taken from the underway system every 6h. The sample bottles were rinsed 3 times and filled to the shoulder of the bottle, then sealed with parafilm. As we run out of parafilm, we sealed the bottles with cling film and duct tape (Figure 19).. Sampling of $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ stopped after Station 40 when the available 198 bottles were filled. The bottles were transported back to Paris for analysis.

Figure 19: Sealing of $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ sample bottle after the parafilm was used up.

13 Methane

Compiled by Marcel du Plessis

Team Gothenburg was responsible for the sampling of methane with the aim to understand methane's presence in the Southern Ocean, whether seeps exist, its behaviour in the water column, and whether climate change is causing methane sinks to thaw (much like the permafrost). Sampling locations are shown in Figure 20.

Figure 20: SO-CHIC methane sampling map with RTopo-2.0 bedrock topography, with CTD methane sampling stations indicated by crosses.

Sampling of dissolved gases takes precedence ahead of chlorophyll, salinity, and other tracers that are less adversely impacted by atmospheric interaction once a Niskin bottle seal is released. In the case of sampling multiple gases, two Niskin bottles were fired at the same depth. Samples vials are filled directly using CTD tubing (without bubbles in tubing) with a gentle flow. The bottles are overflowed three times, with sample presenting a convex meniscus (see Figure 21, Type B) before spiking with 100 μL ZnCl_2 and quickly crimped to avoid trapping bubbles.

Figure 21: Methane sampling meniscus type.

The vials are stored upside-down in a dark and cool space until they are brought back to Gothenburg, where they will be analysed.

14 Glider/Sailbuoy Operations

Compiled by Marcel du Plessis

Team Gothenburg was responsible for deploying instruments for two research interests: (1) characterise the meridional gradient across the northern Maud Rise front and (2) to initiate a full seasonal cycle monitoring of the Polar Upwelling Zone (PUZ) to study the impact of small scale ocean processes on heat and carbon fluxes. Through these combined deployments, the following platforms were deployed on the SO-CHIC cruise:

1. Two buoyancy-driven gliders (Seagliders)
2. One uncrewed surface vehicle (Sailbuoy)

In addition to the platform deployments, calibration CTDs were taken, which followed the procedures for water sampling depths for dissolved oxygen, salinity and chlorophyll. Issues with the onboard Titrimo made bottle measurements of dissolved oxygen unavailable for analysis. A summary of deployments are shown in Table 8.

Figure 22: Deployment locations of the three autonomous robots during the SO-CHIC cruise represented by the red dots while background color shows the satellite derived chlorophyll-a concentration provided by Sentinel 3A, 3B and NOAA-20 VIIRS between 1-13 January 2022. The southern location represents the deployment of one Seaglider (SG640) and Sailbuoy (SB1812) while the northern dot a Seaglider (SG675). See Table 1 for their locations.

Figure 23: SG640 on the heli-deck undergoing testing on the SO-CHIC cruise.

14.1 Seagliders

The Seaglider is a buoyancy glider that samples between the surface and 1000 m in a V-shaped profile. It dives or climbs by pumping oil between internal/external bladders to change its buoyancy, accompanied by battery movement that can change the pitch and roll. It is a largely autonomous system, communicating via satellite at the end of each dive to transfer data and pick up commands such as targets to aim for and sampling rates for the science sensors. The data from the two Seagliders deployed during SO-CHIC cruise are uploaded to the Hydroid basestations and then shown on the University of Washington IOP server. Preliminary science plots are shown at www.roammiz.com.

Both gliders were equipped with Seabird CT sails, Aanderaa dissolved oxygen optodes (AA4831), PAR sensors and WetLabs triplet ECOpuck (measures responses in 470, 695 and 700 nm wavelengths that correspond to chlorophyll, coloured dissolved organic matter and backscatter). To run pre-deployment tests, the gliders must be placed in a position on the heli-deck where they are able to connect to Iridium satellites in the region. We found that the port side of the heli-deck, away from the main structure of the ship, was initially sufficient for this but struggled to option Iridium connection with the error `NO_CARRIER` occurring regularly. The position was then changed to have the glider at the aft of the heli-deck which improved communications. This position was adopted for the remained of the tests.

Platform	Serial #	Sensors	Deployment location	Deployment time
Seaglider	SG640	CTD, EcoPuck, dissolved oxygen, PAR	63° 27.63 S 02° 26.59 E	2022-01-10 15:33 GMT
Sailbuoy	SB1812	Surface TS, Airmar, ADCP	63° 27.51 S 02° 26.54 E	2022-01-10 15:00 GMT
Seaglider	SG675	TS, fluorescence, backscatter, dissolved oxygen, PAR		

Table 8: Platforms deployed during SO-CHIC cruise, including sensors, deployment date and location.

Figure 24: Deployment of SG640 using the quick release off the aft crane.

14.1.1 Deployment procedure

Following a completed Sealaunch procedure and after receiving the “OK to launch” from pilots back on land, the serial cable is disconnected from the glider and the glider is carried down the stairs to the poop deck. Here the wings and rudder can be attached and the sensor caps removed. The gliders were lowered using the aft A-frame and were deployed using a quick release that was fastened around the lifting point on the rudder (Figure 24). After deployment the ship moved forwards at 0.5-1 knots whilst the on-board team observed how the glider was sitting in the water and confirmed to pilots on land that the first dive could be initiated. Whilst the ship is still on station and the glider is on its first few dives, a calibration CTD should be taken (ideally within 4 hours of deployment for best practices of chlorophyll a calibrations).

14.1.2 Typical timings for a deployment

T-1 day:	Run any remaining hardware self-tests and/or simulation dives. Pilots clean basestation and prepare cmdfiles for the Sealaunch
T-2 hours:	Take Seaglider out onto heli-deck, connect and prepare pilots for Sealaunch
T-1.5 hours:	Initiate Sealaunch
Approx T-1 hour:	Receive prompt “Pilots to give OK to launch?”
T-30 mins:	Move Seaglider down to Poop Deck, attach wings and rudder
T-10 mins:	Remove sensor caps and attach quick release.

Figure 25: Buoyancy position of SG640 in the water after 5 minutes.

14.1.3 Pre-deployment checks

Following seatrials in Cape Town, self tests and sim dives were performed on SG675 and SG640 on 5 and 6 January 2022. All tests were passed by the gliders. Firmware changes were also made to SG640, with 66.14 Eagleray ICE firmware being uploaded and installed to ensure that the ice software was available.

14.1.4 Deployment of Seaglider SG640

At the first deployment site, SG640 was deployed in sea state and weather conditions that were excellent with waves smaller than 0.5 m and low winds. SG640 was released from the aft crane using a quick release clip. The glider took approximately 5 minutes to fill with water and to be confirmed to have a good position in the water. Upon confirmation with the piloting team back on land, the glider was placed on her first dive. The ship slowly moved away from SG640 at a speed of 1 knot. The ship team noted that SG640 surfaced early by around 10 minutes. The pilot team identified this as C_VBD that was too low, and was corrected. A CTD cast was taken after three dives were completed and the pilots were happy with the behaviour of SG640.

14.1.5 Deployment of Seaglider SG675

At the northern deployment site, SG675 was deployed in sea state and weather conditions that were good with waves smaller around 2 m and moderate winds. SG675 was released from the aft crane using a quick release clip. We used a thinner rope than we did with SG640 to clip the glider to the quick release and the glider released much better. The glider took approximately 3 minutes to fill with water and to be confirmed to have a good position in the water. Upon confirmation with the piloting team back on land, the glider was placed on her first dive. Sea state made observing the glider difficult

Figure 26: Sailbuoy tied down on the heli-deck undergoing testing.

and we could not see her surfacing from dive 1. The ship slowly moved away from SG675 at a speed of 1 knot and one minute after deployment the ship stopped to allow us to keep eyes on the glider. The ship team noted that SG675 dived at the correct time according to the information provided the pilot team. A CTD cast was taken after two following deployments were completed. The pilots were initially unhappy with the behaviour of SG675 due to a lack communications but this was determined to be a result of reduced satellites in the region and the decision was made to leave the glider out.

14.2 Sailbuoy

The Sailbuoy is a 2m long (60 kg) autonomous surface platform manufactured by Offshore Sensing. It is effectively a small sailing boat, capturing power from the wind to travel forwards. It is equipped with solar panels to charge the two 14V batteries that separately power the autopilot and the datalogger. It carries an Airmar WX-200 Ultrasonic Weather Station, mounted on a mast 0.70 m above MSL and an Aandera DCPS to measure horizontal velocity across 40 bins. The instrument is designed for moving platforms, with the ability to dynamically correct winds using an internal compass and correct up to a 30° pitch in rough seas. The sensor outputs apparent and true wind speed, wind gust (maximum wind speed over the 15-minute sampling period) and direction (up to 40 m s⁻¹), barometric pressure, air temperature, surface TS and currents and GPS location. Each sensor samples at 1 Hz and is then averaged over 15-min bins before transmitting data back to shore. In the keel bulb there is a Neil Brown Ocean Sensors, Inc. CT cell that measures surface ocean temperature and salinity.

14.2.1 Pre-deployment checks

The Sailbuoy was turned on during the morning of the deployment by removing both magnetic switches to ensure communications to pilots back on shore were active and working. Confirmation on the ship of rudder movement was also made. When these communications were confirmed, the Sailbuoy was moved downstairs to fix the sail, sheets and a final check of fastenings.

In the run up to deployment, several alterations were made to the Sailbuoy configurations. DCPS datalogger timeout rate, cell spacing, beam output and cell number were altered to ensure functioning sensors.

14.2.2 Deployment

Deployment followed previous procedures used on the SA Agulhas II, where a quick release was attached to the weight bearing eye at the stern of the Sailbuoy, with a secondary rope at the bow. The Sailbuoy was carefully lowered into the ocean whilst the ship was travelling forward at a rate of 1 knot. The Sailbuoy was programmed to head straight to the northern end of its line of transect.

Figure 27: Deployment of the Sailbuoy on the aft crane using a quick release to the stern of the vehicle.

Figure 28: Sailbuoy sitting in the water and sailing away from the ship.

15 ASFAR (Autonomous System For Argo floats Release)

Compiled by Sebastian Lavanchy

The ASFAR device was designed at LOCEAN to sit at the ocean bottom and release three of the Argo floats at a specified time.

The principal components of the ASFAR float are shown in Figure 29.

15.1 Preparation before deployment

1. Argos beacon switched ON and fixed on structure
2. Safety Kevlar rope fixed on all deep arvor
3. Caps removed on all deep arvor(CTD + optode) and on RBR CTD(optode)
4. ASFAR brought close to the A-Frame
5. Screw and line removed

Date	11.01.2021
Site	2
Station	27
ASFAR deployment time	13:09 GMT
Latitude	63° 39.456' S
Longitude	02° 26.601' E
Depth EA600	3786m
Depth CTD	3748m
Altimeter CTD	9.7m
Boat speed	0.03K
Heading	139.7°
Wind Speed	19.05K
Wind Dir	146°
Sea State	Slight(0.5m to 1.5m)

Table 9: Deployment details of the ASFAR.

Figure 29: ASFAR before deployment.

15.2 Deployment

1. Double release hooks connected to the ASFAR

2. Two temporary lines installed to maintain ASFAR position

3. ASFAR brought overboard

4. ASFAR lowered into the water and released

5. ASFAR deployed

15.2.1 Notes

One of the temporary lines got stuck at its extremity to the structure. The line was cut directly. Approximately 5 meters of line went down with the ASFAR.

Burnwire of L2 broke during the first attempt. The Asfar was spinning and touched the back of the boat. No damage on L2 deep armor.

New burnwire installed and tested with multimeter.

16 Carioca

Compiled by Sebastian Lavanchy

CARIOCA – CARbone Interface OCean Atmosphere

SN 17 CARIO 01/ Argos F1B445F – 160702 (130kg)

16.1 Preparation before deployment

1. Poison capsule installed
2. Optode cap removed
3. Weather station plastic wrap removed
4. Salt water inserted in the two bottom and middle holes.
5. Weather station cable connected to power plug
6. Internal time set with computer
7. Prepare sea anchor

8. Sea anchor connected to the buoy, shackle secured

16.2 Deployment

Date	23.01.2021
Site	1
Station	82
Sea anchor deployment time	14:20 GMT
Carioca deployment time	14:21 GMT
Latitude	53° 59.688' S
Longitude	00° 02.081' W
Depth EA600	2455m
Boat speed	1K
Heading	277.5°
Wind Speed	33.05K
Wind Dir	302°
Sea State	Slight(0.5m to 1.5m)

1. Release hook connected to the handling ring(weather station side)

2. Carioca brought over board with the A-frame and maintained with a temporary line.

3. Sea anchor deployed

4. Temporary line removed, Carioca rotated at 180°

5. Carioca lowered at 1m above the water and released

6. Carioca deployed

17 Deep Arvor Floats

Compiled by Sebastian Lavanchy

Four Deep Arvors were deployed. Details of the 4 floats are provided in Tables 11 to 13.

Figure 30: Deep Arvor before and during deployment.

17.1 Preparation and deployment

1. Out of the box visual inspection
2. Caps removed (CTD 3x + DO)
3. Deep Arvor placed on open sky area for self-test
4. Magnet removed
5. Microvalve and pump checked
6. float self-test sequence achieved, Buzzer activate
7. Boat moving at 1Knot
8. Deep Arvor deployed from A-frame with release hook
9. Buoyancy checked

Site	2
Station	2
FLOAT	DEEP ARVOR
WMO	6902889
SERIAL	AD2700-18FR002
IMEI	300234065791470
Comment after visual inspection of the float	OK
Comment after visual inspection of the ballast	OK
Deployment mission name (cruise name)	SO-CHIC
Deployment ship name	AGULHAS II
Name of the operator in charge of the deployment	Sébastien LAVANCHY
CTD or XBT profile done during deployment (yes/no)	Yes
Magnet removal time (dd/mm/yyyy hh:mm)	07.01.2022 11:02
Comment on float internal checks (valve and pump actions, argos transmission check)	OK
Deployment time (dd/mm/yyyy hh:mm)	07.01.2022 11:11
Deployment latitude (dd°mm.mm N/S or dd°mm'ss" N/S)	67°59.005'S
Deployment longitude (ddd°mm.mm E/W or ddd°mm'ss" E/W)	00°28.006'E
Buoyancy description	OK
Deployment method (release box, manual, expendable cardboard, etc...)	MANUAL
Deployment height (m)	1
Ship speed (kts)	2
Wind speed (Beaufort)	2
Sea state (calm, smooth, slight, moderate, rough, very rough, high, very high, phenomenal)	Slight(0.5m to 1.5m)
Bathymetry at deployment position (m)	4538
Number of days until the first ascending profile (copy of the PM2 parameter value)	2
Miscellaneous comment on the deployment	

Table 10: Deployment details of the Deep Arvor SN AD2700-18FR002.

Site	2
Station	2
FLOAT	DEEP ARVOR
WMO	6902890
SERIAL	AD2700-18FR003
IMEI	3005534061369070
Comment after visual inspection of the float	OK
Comment after visual inspection of the ballast	OK
Deployment mission name (cruise name)	SO-CHIC
Deployment ship name	AGULHAS II
Name of the operator in charge of the deployment	Sébastien LAVANCHY
CTD or XBT profile done during deployment (yes/no)	Yes
Magnet removal time (dd/mm/yyyy hh:mm)	07.01.2022 11:14
Comment on float internal checks (valve and pump actions, argos transmission check)	OK
Deployment time (dd/mm/yyyy hh:mm)	07.01.2022 11:19
Deployment latitude (dd°mm.mm N/S or dd°mm'ss" N/S)	67°58.793'S
Deployment longitude (ddd°mm.mm E/W or ddd°mm'ss" E/W)	00°27.803'E
Buoyancy description	OK
Deployment method (release box, manual, expendable cardboard, etc...)	MANUAL
Deployment height (m)	1
Ship speed (kts)	2
Wind speed (Beaufort)	2
Sea state (calm, smooth, slight, moderate, rough, very rough, high, very high,	Slight(0.5m to 1.5m)
Bathymetry at deployment position (m)	4541
Number of days until the first ascending profile (copy of the PM2 parameter value)	2
Miscellaneous comment on the deployment	

Table 11: Deployment details of the Deep Arvor SN AD2700-18FR003.

Site	2
Station	3
FLOAT	DEEP ARVOR
WMO	6902893
SERIAL	AD2700-18FR006
IMEI	300234065896790
Comment after visual inspection of the float	OK
Comment after visual inspection of the ballast	OK
Deployment mission name (cruise name)	SO-CHIC
Deployment ship name	AGULHAS II
Name of the operator in charge of the deployment	Sébastien LAVANCHY
CTD or XBT profile done during deployment (yes/no)	Yes
Magnet removal time (dd/mm/yyyy hh:mm)	07.01.2022 17:37
Comment on float internal checks (valve and pump actions, argos transmission check)	OK
Deployment time (dd/mm/yyyy hh:mm)	07.01.2022 17:45
Deployment latitude (dd°mm.mm N/S or dd°mm'ss" N/S)	67°29.986'S
Deployment longitude (ddd°mm.mm E/W or ddd°mm'ss" E/W)	00°03.500'E
Buoyancy description	OK
Deployment method (release box, manual, expendable cardboard, etc...)	MANUAL
Deployment height (m)	1
Ship speed (kts)	1
Wind speed (Beaufort)	3
Sea state (calm, smooth, slight, moderate, rough, very rough, high, very high, phenomenal)	Slight(0.5m to 1.5m)
Bathymetry at deployment position (m)	4621
Number of days until the first ascending profile (copy of the PM2 parameter value)	2
Miscellaneous comment on the deployment	

Table 12: Deployment details of the Deep Arvor SN AD2700-18FR006.

Site	2
Station	3
FLOAT	DEEP ARVOR
WMO	6902980
SERIAL	AD2700-18FR019
IMEI	300234067017460
Comment after visual inspection of the float	OK
Comment after visual inspection of the ballast	OK
Deployment mission name (cruise name)	SO-CHIC
Deployment ship name	AGULHAS II
Name of the operator in charge of the deployment	Sébastien LAVANCHY
CTD or XBT profile done during deployment (yes/no)	Yes
Magnet removal time (dd/mm/yyyy hh:mm)	07.01.2022 17:28
Comment on float internal checks (valve and pump actions, argos transmission check)	OK
Deployment time (dd/mm/yyyy hh:mm)	07.01.2022 17:35
Deployment latitude (dd°mm.mm N/S or dd°mm'ss" N/S)	67°29.988'S
Deployment longitude (ddd°mm.mm E/W or ddd°mm'ss" E/W)	00°03.161'E
Buoyancy description	OK
Deployment method (release box, manual, expendable cardboard, etc...)	MANUAL
Deployment height (m)	1
Ship speed (kts)	1
Wind speed (Beaufort)	2
Sea state (calm, smooth, slight, moderate, rough, very rough, high, very high,	Slight(0.5m to 1.5m)
Bathymetry at deployment position (m)	4622
Number of days until the first ascending profile (copy of the PM2 parameter value)	2
Miscellaneous comment on the deployment	

Table 13: Deployment details of the Deep Arvor SN AD2700-18FR019.

18 Arvor Floats

Compiled by Sebastian Lavanchy

18.1 Preparation and deployment

1. Out of the box visual inspection
2. Caps removed (CTD 3x)
3. Arvor placed on open sky area for self-test
4. Magnet removed
5. Microvalve and pump checked
6. float self-test sequence achieved, Buzzer activated
7. Boat moving at 1Knot
8. Arvor deployed from A-frame with release hook
9. Buoyancy checked

Figure 31: Arvor before and during deployment.

Site	2
Station	5
FLOAT	ARVOR
WMO	6903114
SERIAL	AI2600-21FR001
IMEI	300534060115230
Comment after visual inspection of the float	OK
Comment after visual inspection of the ballast	OK
Deployment mission name (cruise name)	SO-CHIC
Deployment ship name	AGULHAS II
Name of the operator in charge of the deployment	Sébastien LAVANCHY
CTD or XBT profile done during deployment (yes/no)	No
Magnet removal time (dd/mm/yyyy hh:mm)	08.01.2022 18:54
Comment on float internal checks (valve and pump actions, argos transmission check)	OK
Deployment time (dd/mm/yyyy hh:mm)	08.01.2022 19:09
Deployment latitude (dd°mm,mm N/S or dd°mm'ss" N/S)	64°32.659'S
Deployment longitude (ddd°mm,mm E/W or ddd°mm'ss" E/W)	03°12.319'E
Buoyancy description	OK
Deployment method (release box, manual, expendable cardboard, etc...)	MANUAL
Deployment height (m)	1
Ship speed (kts)	1
Wind speed (Beaufort)	6
Sea state (calm, smooth, slight, moderate, rough, very rough, high, very high, phenomenal)	moderate(2m to 3m)
Bathymetry at deployment position (m)	2119
Number of days until the first ascending profile (copy of the PM2 parameter value)	2
Miscellaneous comment on the deployment	

Table 14: Deployment details of the Deep Arvor SN AI2600-21FR001.

Site	2
Station	27
FLOAT	ARVOR
WMO	6903115
SERIAL	AI2600-21FR002
IMEI	300534060116240
Comment after visual inspection of the float	OK
Comment after visual inspection of the ballast	OK
Deployment mission name (cruise name)	SO-CHIC
Deployment ship name	AGULHAS II
Name of the operator in charge of the deployment	Sébastien LAVANCHY
CTD or XBT profile done during deployment (yes/no)	Yes
Magnet removal time (dd/mm/yyyy hh:mm)	11.01.2022 13:23
Comment on float internal checks (valve and pump actions, argos transmission check)	OK
Deployment time (dd/mm/yyyy hh:mm)	11.01.2022 13:30
Deployment latitude (dd°mm,mm N/S or dd°mm'ss" N/S)	63°39.579'S
Deployment longitude (ddd°mm,mm E/W or ddd°mm'ss" E/W)	02°26.877'E
Buoyancy description	OK
Deployment method (release box, manual, expendable cardboard, etc...)	MANUAL
Deployment height (m)	1
Ship speed (kts)	1
Wind speed (Beaufort)	4
Sea state (calm, smooth, slight, moderate, rough, very rough, high, very high,	Slight(0.5m to 1.5m)
Bathymetry at deployment position (m)	3775
Number of days until the first ascending profile (copy of the PM2 parameter value)	2
Miscellaneous comment on the deployment	

Table 15: Deployment details of the Deep Arvor SN AI2600-21FR002.

Site	2
Station	27
FLOAT	ARVOR
WMO	6903116
SERIAL	AI2600-21FR003
IMEI	300534060114220
Comment after visual inspection of the float	OK
Comment after visual inspection of the ballast	OK
Deployment mission name (cruise name)	SO-CHIC
Deployment ship name	AGULHAS II
Name of the operator in charge of the deployment	Sébastien LAVANCHY
CTD or XBT profile done during deployment (yes/no)	Yes
Magnet removal time (dd/mm/yyyy hh:mm)	11.01.2022 13:33
Comment on float internal checks (valve and pump actions, argos transmission check)	OK
Deployment time (dd/mm/yyyy hh:mm)	11.01.2022 13:42
Deployment latitude (dd°mm,mm N/S or dd°mm'ss" N/S)	63°39.722'S
Deployment longitude (ddd°mm,mm E/W or ddd°mm'ss" E/W)	02°27.160'E
Buoyancy description	OK
Deployment method (release box, manual, expendable cardboard, etc...)	MANUAL
Deployment height (m)	1
Ship speed (kts)	1
Wind speed (Beaufort)	4
Sea state (calm, smooth, slight, moderate, rough, very rough, high, very high, phenomenal)	Slight(0.5m to 1.5m)
Bathymetry at deployment position (m)	3768
Number of days until the first ascending profile (copy of the PM2 parameter value)	2
Miscellaneous comment on the deployment	

Table 16: Deployment details of the Deep Arvor SN AI2600-21FR003.

Site	2
Station	27
FLOAT	ARVOR
WMO	6903117
SERIAL	AI2600-21FR004
IMEI	300534060118250
Comment after visual inspection of the float	OK
Comment after visual inspection of the ballast	OK
Deployment mission name (cruise name)	SO-CHIC
Deployment ship name	AGULHAS II
Name of the operator in charge of the deployment	Sébastien LAVANCHY
CTD or XBT profile done during deployment (yes/no)	Yes
Magnet removal time (dd/mm/yyyy hh:mm)	11.01.2022 13:54
Comment on float internal checks (valve and pump actions, argos transmission check)	OK
Deployment time (dd/mm/yyyy hh:mm)	11.01.2022 14:01
Deployment latitude (dd°mm,mm N/S or dd°mm'ss" N/S)	63°40.256'S
Deployment longitude (ddd°mm,mm E/W or ddd°mm'ss" E/W)	02°28.151'E
Buoyancy description	OK
Deployment method (release box, manual, expendable cardboard, etc...)	MANUAL
Deployment height (m)	1
Ship speed (kts)	1
Wind speed (Beaufort)	4
Sea state (calm, smooth, slight, moderate, rough, very rough, high, very high, phenomenal)	Slight(0.5m to 1.5m)
Bathymetry at deployment position (m)	3647
Number of days until the first ascending profile (copy of the PM2 parameter value)	2
Miscellaneous comment on the deployment	

Table 17: Deployment details of the Deep Arvor SN AI2600-21FR004.

Site	2
Station	27
FLOAT	ARVOR
WMO	6903118
SERIAL	AI2600-21FR005
IMEI	300534060115230
Comment after visual inspection of the float	OK
Comment after visual inspection of the ballast	OK
Deployment mission name (cruise name)	SO-CHIC
Deployment ship name	AGULHAS II
Name of the operator in charge of the deployment	Sébastien LAVANCHY
CTD or XBT profile done during deployment (yes/no)	Yes
Magnet removal time (dd/mm/yyyy hh:mm)	11.01.2022 14:04
Comment on float internal checks (valve and pump actions, argos transmission check)	OK
Deployment time (dd/mm/yyyy hh:mm)	11.01.2022 14:10
Deployment latitude (dd°mm,mm N/S or dd°mm'ss" N/S)	64°40.376'S
Deployment longitude (ddd°mm,mm E/W or ddd°mm'ss" E/W)	02°28.377'E
Buoyancy description	OK
Deployment method (release box, manual, expendable cardboard, etc...)	MANUAL
Deployment height (m)	1
Ship speed (kts)	1
Wind speed (Beaufort)	4
Sea state (calm, smooth, slight, moderate, rough, very rough, high, very high, phenomenal)	Slight(0.5m to 1.5m)
Bathymetry at deployment position (m)	3530
Number of days until the first ascending profile (copy of the PM2 parameter value)	2
Miscellaneous comment on the deployment	

Table 18: Deployment details of the Deep Arvor SN AI2600-21FR005.

19 BioArgo

Compiled by Sebastian Lavanchy

19.1 Preparation and deployment

1. Out of the box visual inspection
2. Caps removed (CTD 3x, Optical 2x), Note: no optode on BioArgo
3. BioArgo placed on open sky area for self-test
4. Magnet removed and put on Bluetooth
5. BioArgo connected to computer
6. Auto test command sent
7. float self-test sequence achieved, magnet removed
8. Boat moving at 1Knot
9. BioArgo deployed from A-frame with release hook
10. Buoyancy checked

Figure 32: Bioargo before and during deployment.

Site	2
Station	5
FLOAT	CTS4
WMO	6903129
SERIAL	lovbio097 OIN-15-S4-02
IMEI	?
Comment after visual inspection of the float	OK
Comment after visual inspection of the ballast	OK
Deployment mission name (cruise name)	SO-CHIC
Deployment ship name	AGULHAS II
Name of the operator in charge of the deployment	Sébastien LAVANCHY
CTD or XBT profile done during deployment (yes/no)	Yes
Magnet removal time (dd/mm/yyyy hh:mm)	08.01.2022 19:12
Comment on float internal checks (valve and pump actions, argos transmission check)	OK
Deployment time (dd/mm/yyyy hh:mm)	08.01.2022 19:23
Deployment latitude (dd°mm,mm N/S or dd°mm'ss" N/S)	64°32.860'S
Deployment longitude (ddd°mm,mm E/W or ddd°mm'ss" E/W)	03°12.533'E
Buoyancy description	OK
Deployment method (release box, manual, expendable cardboard, etc...)	MANUAL
Deployment height (m)	1
Ship speed (kts)	1
Wind speed (Beaufort)	5
Sea state (calm, smooth, slight, moderate, rough, very rough, high, very high, phenomenal)	Moderate(1.5m to 2.5m)
Bathymetry at deployment position (m)	2119
Number of days until the first ascending profile (copy of the PM2 parameter value)	2
Miscellaneous comment on the deployment	

Table 19: Deployment details of the BioArgo SN lovbio097 OIN-15-S4-02.

Site	1
Station	82
FLOAT	CTS4
WMO	6903128
SERIAL	lovbio096 OIN-15-S4-01
IMEI	
Comment after visual inspection of the float	OK
Comment after visual inspection of the ballast	OK
Deployment mission name (cruise name)	SO-CHIC
Deployment ship name	AGULHAS II
Name of the operator in charge of the deployment	Sébastien LAVANCHY
CTD or XBT profile done during deployment (yes/no)	Yes
Magnet removal time (dd/mm/yyyy hh:mm)	23.01.2022 14:26
Comment on float internal checks (valve and pump actions, argos transmission check)	OK
Deployment time (dd/mm/yyyy hh:mm)	23.01.2022 14:37
Deployment latitude (dd°mm,mm N/S or dd°mm'ss" N/S)	53°59.665'S
Deployment longitude (ddd°mm,mm E/W or ddd°mm'ss" E/W)	00°02.229'W
Buoyancy description	OK
Deployment method (release box, manual, expendable cardboard, etc...)	MANUAL
Deployment height (m)	1
Ship speed (kts)	1
Wind speed (Beaufort)	4
Sea state (calm, smooth, slight, moderate, rough, very rough, high, very high, phenomenal)	Slight(0.5m to 1.5m)
Bathymetry at deployment position (m)	2458
Number of days until the first ascending profile (copy of the PM2 parameter value)	2
Miscellaneous comment on the deployment	ADOPT A FLOAT

Table 20: Deployment details of the BioArgo SN lovbio096 OIN-15-S4-01.

20 UTempBuoy

Compiled by Sebastian Lavanchy

There were three types of UTempBuoys deployed during SO-CHIC, shown in Figure 33.

Figure 33: The 3 types of UTempBuoys: 6 x iceBT60/40-17T3P (left); 6 x iceBTC2/40-11T0P (middle); 6 x iceBTC5/40-11T0P (right).

Figure 34: UTempBuoy deployments.

20.1 Preparation and Deployment

1. Out of the box visual inspection
2. Plastics films and tape removed
3. Buoy placed on open sky area
4. Magnet removed
5. E-mail received(every 5 min the first hour, and after hourly)
6. Boat moving at 1 Knot
7. Weight and temp chain deployed first over board
8. Buoy dropped into the water

Platform ID	Iridium ID	Type	Depl Lat	Depl Long	Depl time, GMT
226786	300234061165580	iceBT60/40-17T3P	64° 32.596'S	03°12.596'E	19:26 08/01/22
226784	300234061166580	iceBT60/40-17T3P	64° 32.961'S	03°12.656'E	19:30 08/01/22
227129	300234068141290	iceBTC2/40-11T0P	64° 32.997'S	03°12.701'E	19:33 08/01/22

Table 21: Deployment details of the UtempBuoy for Site2 CTD Station 5 on the 08/01/2022.

Platform ID	Iridium ID	Type	Depl Lat	Depl Long	Depl time, GMT
226785	300234061166530	iceBT60/40-17T3P	63° 39.492'S	02°26.672'E	13:23 11/01/22
226783	300234061167580	iceBT60/40-17T3P	63° 39.603'S	02°26.930'E	13:32 11/01/22
226782	300234061168580	iceBT60/40-17T3P	63° 40.159'S	02°27.973'E	13:53 11/01/22
226781	300234061169580	iceBT60/40-17T3P	63° 40.289'S	02°28.217'E	14:04 11/01/22
227128	300234068141310	iceBTC5/40-11T0P	63° 40.410'S	02°28.445'E	14:13 11/01/22

Table 22: Deployment details of the UtempBuoy for Site2 CTD Station 27 on the 11/01/2022.

21 PROPOL (Profiler for Polynya)

Compiled by Sebastian Lavanchy

A schematic of the PROPOL is shown in Figure 35. It is essentially a bioargo float (LOVBIO_068 SN: OIN13-S4-08) attached to a tether cable, which is moored to the ocean bottom. It is programmed to profile throughout the winter months in the MRP region.

Figure 35: Schematic of PROPOL deployment strategy.

21.1 Preparation Before Deployment

1. Buoyancy test at Penguins Bukta, the 06.01.2022 at 10.19 GMT

2. RBR Duo fixed Below 50 cm bellow trawl float

3. Weigh brought to the A-frame, Shackles checked and secured

4. Acoustic releaser and yellow spheres connected to the weight, Shackles checked and secured

5. Caps removed (CTD 3x)

6. Propol placed on open sky area for self-test

7. Magnet removed and put on Bluetooth

8. Propol connected to computer

9. Auto test command sent
10. Propol self-test sequence achieved, magnet removed

==~==~==~==~==~==~==~==~== PuTTY log 2022.01.08 06:30:54 ==~==~==~==~==~==~==~==~==

```
<ER>
!?ns
<NS 1308>
SERIAL NUMBER Measure: 1308
!g
<Parameters loaded>
****AUTOTEST****

< TEST EEPROM >
< EEPROM: OK >

< TEST FLASH >
< FLASH: OK (2E65) >

< TEST EXT. BLADDER >
< EXT. BLADDER: OK >

< TEST VACUUM >
< VACUUM: OK (655) >

< TEST BATTERY >
< BATTERY: OK (108) >

< TEST GPS >
< GPS: OK >

< TEST MODEM RUDICS CONNECTION >
< RUDICS: OK >

< TEST MEASURE BOARD >
< MEASURE BOARD: OK >

*****MISSION START*****
```

21.2 Deployment

1. First try Upper line reel broke, we recovered the propol(magnet on) and stopped the deployment.

2. Propol self-test, caps off, magnet off
3. Propol deployed

4. Upper line deployed by hand

5. Upper line connected to the 3 red trawl floats, and deployed. Shackles and swivel checked, and secured.

6. Lower line deployed by Hand

7. Yellow spheres and acoustic releaser deployed. Shackle checked and secured

8. Weight connected to mooring line

9. Weight deployed

21.3 Triangulation

Triangulation of the mooring was carried out by listening to the acoustic release at three positions around the mooring deployment location. These are shown in Tables 23 to 25. The triangulation result is shown on Figure 36.

Note: The acoustic listener had its cable cut by the ship's starboard thruster due to a change in the bridge officer who had not been informed of the triangulation operation.

Range measurement	Coordinate
2331	64° 32.138'S
2329	03° 15.452' E

Table 23: PROPOL triangulation point 1 range and position.

Range measurement	Coordinate
2663	64° 31.147'S
2664	03° 15.878' E

Table 24: PROPOL triangulation point 2 range and position.

Range measurement	Coordinate
3350	64° 31.746'S
(2456) <u>pinger cable broken</u>	03° 11.334' E

Table 25: PROPOL triangulation point 3 range and position.

Figure 36: PROPOL triangulation pattern indicating the position of the mooring.

22 Upward Looking Sonar (ULS)

Compiled by Sebastian Lavanchy

SN 54097/129 - 100kg with frame

Figure 37: ULS deployment schematic.

22.1 Preparation before deployment

1. RBR duo installed on ULS structure

2. ULS protection and pressure sensor lid removed
3. Anchor brought to the A-frame, Shackles checked and secured
4. Upper line connected to ULS Structure and deployed on the deck

5. Releaser installed between upper line and lower line. Shackles checked and secured

22.2 Deployment

Date	08.01.2021
Site	2
Station	5
Deployment start time	17:14 GMT
Start Latitude	64° 31.0' S
Start Longitude	03° 10.5' E
ULS in water time	17:16 GMT
Latitude at 17:21	64° 31.185' S
Longitude at 17:21	03° 10.767' E
Line connected to weight time	17:58 GMT
Connection Latitude	64° 31.724' S
Connection Longitude	03° 11.364' E
Weight deployed time	18:49 GMT
Deployment Latitude	64° 33.074' S
Deployment Longitude	03° 12.856' E
Depth EA600	2121m
Depth EA600 at propol station	2114
Depth CTD at propol station	2064.8m
Altimeter CTD at propol station	9.4m
Boat speed	1.02K
Heading	149.5°
Wind Speed	20.6 K
Wind Dir	159.1°
Sea State	Moderate (1.5m to 2.5m)

Table 26: Details of the ULS deployment.

1. Release hook connected to ULS structure

2. ULS brought overboard

3. ULS Lowered 0.5 m above the water and released

4. ULS and Acoustic releaser into the water

5. Weight connected to mooring line

6. Weight deployed

23 Air-Sea Interaction Profiler

Compiled by Brian Ward and Anneke ten Doeschate

The Air-Sea Interaction Profiler (ASIP) is a unique instrument for the study of the upper ocean.

ASIP had been set up our equipment in the heli-hangar of the vessel.

We had been having issues with a pressure sensor on ASIP, which is a critical data stream for operation in the ocean. On January 13th we had been able to fix this issue, and had planned to reassemble ASIP and ready it for testing the next morning.

The following morning the ship commenced a test of the water cannons on the fore and aft decks. It appears that this test had the effect of causing a valve to rupture. This valve controlled the flow of water to the fire sprinklers in the heli-hanger. The water pressure to the sprinklers was 13 bar.

The type of water in the heli-hanger sprinkler system was seawater.

The ruptured valve resulted in a deluge of seawater to rain down on ASIP's electronics boards, the battery compartment, and all components and materials that were on the bench.

Seawater is electrically conductive. Seawater is also corrosive, and as seawater is a fluid, it will work its way into the smallest crevices between components on electronics circuit boards.

This accident resulted in the complete destruction of all electronics boards on ASIP to the point where they are rendered useless.

As such no data was acquired with ASIP.